

**AN ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF EXTERNAL DEBT ON ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN NIGERIA (1981 – 2016)**

BY

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FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

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BENIN CITY

OCTOBER, 2018

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**BEING A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
ECONOMICS AND STATISTICS, FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES,
UNIVERSITY OF BENIN, BENIN CITY, IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF
THE REQUIREMENT FOR AWARD OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCE
DEGREE (B.Sc) IN ECONOMICS AND STATISTICS.**

OCTOBER, 2018

CERTIFICATION

We the undersigned persons certify that this research was carried out by **NWANKWO GLORY EBUBE** with matriculation number **SSC1406302** in the department of Economic and Statistics, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Benin is approved and therefore considered adequate in scope and content for the in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of Bachelor Of Science (B.Sc) Degree in Economics And Statistics.

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DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to Almighty God, the author and finisher of our faith, who has made it possible for me to achieve this much. And to my mother Mrs. BenedethNwankwo who sacrificed materially for my success in school and also to my dearest uncle Igwe Humphrey OlunaEjesieme for his fatherly assistance.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I am most thankful to God Almighty for granting me the wisdom, strength and provision through my period in this citadel of learning.

I sincerely appreciate my project supervisor, Dr (Mrs). E.I. Iziliein, whose wisdom and approach prompted the successful completion of this study. I am grateful to you ma, for imparting in me the spirit of hard work and also for teaching me the rudiments of project writing. I am also grateful to my Head of Department, Dr Clement Ighodaro, for the advisory and disciplinary role he played which imparted in me some sense of time and environment consciousness. It is a great pleasure to acknowledge Prof M.I Obadan, Prof. D.E Oriakhi, Prof. (Mrs) C.E.E Okojie, Prof. Tony Monye-Emina, Dr James Owkeshine, Dr Arodoye, Dr Success, and all other lecturers of this great department, I am proud of you all, and I am indeed grateful for the learning and character we achieved through you all.

My profound gratitude goes to my Uncle, Igwe Humphery Oluna Ejesieme. Uchenna Okonkwo and his wife Mrs. Mary Okonkwo for their support. My beloved mother and senior brother for being my guarantor throughout my stay in uniben, words are not enough to express how grateful I am mother. And also to my elder Miss Esther Eyuiche Nwankwo, thanks for everything. My profound gratitude goes also to my father, Mr Godwin Nwankwo although he is late, daddy your foundational support in my academics is what have kept me going, I love you. Infact the list is endless; I love you all.

A million thanks to my friends, Adorable Maria Inope, Abdulhameed Abu, Uche Austin, Favour Igboamaka and Stephanie Nwaeze, am indeed blessed to have you all, you guys are the best. Life will never fail to favour you all in what you do. My regards to all graduating students of ECOSTAT 2017/2018 session, I wish you all the best in life. I am also thankful to my spiritual

mentor, Pastor AinoAisabu and all other friends at fellowship (Greater Glory Campus Fellowship), and I am indeed grateful also to my friends at Children Evangelism Ministry (CEM), Women Preneur, God bless you all.

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at ascertaining the impact of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria. External debt is a major source of public receipts and financing capital accumulation in any economy, The primary objective of this study is to analyse the impact external debt burden has on economic growth in Nigeria, using data on real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), External Debt, Inflation rate, and government capital expenditure, obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, 2016. Debt Service Payment and gross fixed capital formation were collected from the World Development Index (WDI) 2016. The period of study was 1981-2016. Model was formulated and data were analyzed using Ordinary Least Square. Descriptive statistics, Diagnostic tests were conducted using Augmented Dick Fuller Unit Root Test, Co-integration, and Error Correction Model. The independent variable was RGDP, while the explanatory variables were External Debt Stock, Debt Service Payment inflation rate, government capital expenditure and gross fixed capital formation. We discovered that External Debt in the short and long run, debt service payment, government capital expenditure and gross fixed capital formation had a positive relationship with real Gross Domestic Product. All the variables was statistically significant at 5% significance level apart from Debt service payment variable. While inflation rate has a negative relationship with it and was statistically significant. The study

It is recommended amongst others that Loans contracted should be invested in profitable ventures, which will generate a reasonable amount of money for debt repayment. External debt finance should be used only for projects of highest priority such as mineral resources, education and agricultural projects etc.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

One of the key macroeconomic objectives of a nation is the achievement of sustainable economic growth. To achieve this goal, every Government requires a substantial amount of capital finance through investment expenditures on infrastructural and productive capacity development (Umaru et al, 2013). Consequently, this facilitates the growth of their gross domestic product (GDP), which if persistent should culminate in economic development, a status vigorously pursued by all less developed countries (LDCs), Nigeria inclusive. However, Ayadi & Ayadi (2008) note that the amount of capital available in most developing countries treasury is grossly inadequate to meet their economic growth needs mainly due to their low productivity, low savings and high consumption pattern. Governments therefore resort to borrowing from outside the country to bridge the resource gap.

Countries borrow to promote economic growth and development, by creating conducive environment for people to invest in various sectors of their economies (Umaru et al, 2013). Similarly, Obudah and Tombofa (2013) argued that the specific reasons why countries may borrow include: to be able to finance their reoccurring budget deficit, as a means of deepening their financial markets, to enable them fund the increasing

government expenditures, to enhance their narrow revenue sources and low output productivity which results in poor economic growth. According to Chenery's (1966) Dual-gap theory, governments borrow to augment their limited resources so as to bridge the savings-investment gap.

The Keynesian economics school of thought posits that government borrowing can be used to promote economic growth, through the financing of government deficit expenditures which stimulates aggregate demand and thus encourage increase in private investments. The constant need for governments to borrow in order to finance budget deficit and other macroeconomic objectives has led to the creation of external debt (Osinubi and Olaleru, 2006). Soludo (2003) in Okonjo-Iweala et al (2013) argues that once an initial stock of debt grows to a certain threshold, servicing them becomes a burden, and countries find themselves on the wrong side of the Debt Laffer Curve, with debt crowding out investment and growth. Conversely, Bakare (2011) asserts that a country's indebtedness does not necessarily slow growth, rather it is the nation's inability to optimally utilize these loans to foster economic growth and development and ensure effective servicing of such debt that hampers the benefits derivable from borrowed capital resources.

External debt is a major source of public receipts and financing capital accumulation in any economy (Adepoju et al, 2007). It is a medium used by countries to bridge their deficits and

carry out economic projects that are able to increase the standard of living of the citizenry and promote sustainable growth and development. Hameed, Ashraf and Chaudary (2008) stated that external borrowing ought to accelerate economic growth especially when domestic financing is inadequate. External debt also improves total factor productivity through an increase in output which in turn enhances Gross Domestic product (GDP) growth of a nation. The importance of external debt cannot be overemphasized as it is an ardent booster of growth and thus improves living standards thereby alleviating poverty. Developing countries like Nigeria have often contracted large amount of external debts that has led to the mounting of trade debt arrears at highly concessional interest rates. Gohar and Butt (2012) opined that accumulated debt service payments create a lot of problems for countries especially the developing nations reason being that a debt is actually serviced for more than the amount it was acquired and this slows down the growth process in such nations. The inability of the Nigerian economy to meet its debt service payments obligations has resulted in debt overhang or debt service burden that has militated against her growth and development (Audu, 2004). The genesis of Nigeria's debt service burden dates back to 1978 after a fall in world oil prices. Prior to this occurrence Nigeria had incurred some minor debts from World Bank in 1958 with a loan of US\$28million dollars for railway construction and the Paris Club debtor nations in 1964 from the Italian government with a loan of US\$13.1 million for the construction of the Niger dam. The first major borrowing of US\$1 billion known as the "Jumbo loan" was in 1978 from the International Capital Market (ICM)

(Adesola, 2009). External borrowing has a significant impact on the growth and investment of a nation up to a point where high levels of external debt servicing sets in and affects the growth as the focus moves from financing private investment to repayments of debts. Pattilo, Poirson and Ricci (2002) asserted that at low levels debt has positive effects on growth but above particular points or thresholds accumulated debt begins to have a negative impact on growth. Furthermore Fosu (2009) observed that high debt service payments shifts spending away from health, educational and social sectors. This obscures the motive behind external borrowing which is to boost growth and development rather than get drowned in a pool of debt service payments which eats up most of the nation's resources and hinders growth due to high interest payments on external debt. Nigeria as a developing nation has adopted a number of policies such as the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) of 1986 to liberalize her economy and boost Gross Domestic product (GDP) growth. In a bid to ensure the implementation of these policies the government embarked upon massive borrowings from multilateral sources which resulted in a high external debt service burden and by 1992 Nigeria was classified among the heavily indebted poor countries (HIPC) by the World Bank. According to (Omotoye, Sharma, Ngassam and Eseonu, 2006) Nigeria is the largest debtor nation in sub Saharan Africa. When compared with other sub Saharan nations such as South Africa, Nigeria's external debt stock follows an upward pattern over the years while the former is relatively stabilized (Ayad and Ayadi, 2008). Nigeria's external debt stock rose from US\$28454.8 million in 1997 to US\$310416 .6 and US\$37883.1

million in 2001 and 2004 with 80.3, 64.67 and 52.58 percentages of GDP respectively. On the other hand South Africa's external debt stock stood at US\$25272.4 million, US\$24050 million and US\$27112.4 million in 1997, 2001 and 2004 with 16.98, 20.34 and 12.52 percentages of GDP respectively.

The inability of Nigeria to effectively meet her debt obligations has adverse effect on the economy, as interests arrears accumulate over the years, thereby creating a much greater debt burden on the nation resulting in a greater percent of her revenue being spent on debt service arrears. Audu (2004) opined that the debt service burden has continued to hamper Nigeria's rapid economic development and worsened the social problems; this is because debt servicing crowds out investment and growth. Furthermore, Pattilo et al (2002) assert that at low levels, debt has positive effects on growth but above the threshold point accumulated debt begins to have a negative impact on growth. This therefore has informed the need to embark on the present study with a view to empirically analyze the impact of external debt on economic growth rate (as measured by GDP growth) of Nigeria.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“Huge external debt does not necessarily imply a slow economic growth; it is a nation's inability to meet its debt service payments fueled by inadequate knowledge on the nature, structure and

magnitude of the debt in question” (Were, 2011). It is no exaggeration that this is the major challenge faced by the Nigerian economy. The inability of the Nigerian economy to effectively meet its debt servicing requirements has exposed the nation to a high debt service burden. The resultant effect of this debt service burden creates additional problems for the nation particularly the increasing fiscal deficit which is driven by higher levels of debt servicing. This poses a grave threat to the economy as a large chunk of the nation’s hard earned revenue is being eaten up. Nigeria’s external debt outstanding stood at US\$28.35 million in 2001 which was about 59.4% of GDP from US\$8.5 million in 1980 which was about 14.6% of GDP (WDI 2013). The debt crisis reached its maximum in 2003 when US\$2.3 billion was transferred to service Nigeria’s external debt. In the year 2005 the Paris Club group of creditor nations forgave 60% (US\$18 billion) of US\$30.85 billion debt owed by Nigeria. Despite the debt relief of US\$18 billion received by Nigeria from the Paris club in 2005 the situation remains the same (Bakare, 2010). The question then becomes why has external borrowing not accelerated the pace of growth of the Nigerian economy?

There are various empirical studies that have been conducted to investigate the impact of external debt burden on economic growth in Nigeria and have arrived at different results using the same scope of study (Bhattarchanya & Nguyen, 2003; Fosu, 2007; Hunt, 2007; Ayadi, 2008 Mbah 2016). My research study will focus on the issues in external debt on the Nigerian

economy, determine the relationship between external debt and economic growth by expanding the scope of study beyond what has been done by previous researchers.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In view of the problems of this study, the study is guided by the following research questions:

1. Does a long run relationship exist between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between external debt stock and economic growth in Nigeria?
3. How has external debt service payment impeded economic growth in Nigeria?
4. What are the causes of external debt burden in Nigeria?

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The primary objective of this study is to analyse the impact external debt burden has on economic growth in Nigeria. However other specific objectives of the study include:

1. To examine the long run relationship between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria.
2. To examine the nature of relationship between external debt and economic growth
3. To ascertain the impact of external debt service payment on economic growth of Nigeria.
4. To identify the causes of external debt burden in Nigeria.

1.5 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The hypotheses of this research are stated in null form (Ho) thus:

1. There is no significant long run relationship between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria
2. There is no correlation between external debt stock and economic growth in Nigeria
3. External debt service payment does not impact on economic growth in Nigeria
4. There are no significant causes of external debt burden in Nigeria

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The nature of Nigeria economy has made it to be vulnerable to external shocks. Over the years, the adverse effects of external debt and economic growth related problems on the Nigerian economy are becoming unbearable. So the study will be of importance to educate Nigerians by revealing to them one of the major reasons why Nigerian economy is growing at a very slow rate, which could be traced back to the huge amount of foreign earnings spent on the external debt services instead of spending it on domestic investment. Thus an undocked growth in foreign exchange outflows to service accumulating debt, which will only further entrench under

development of Nigeria economy .This means increasing poverty ,ignorance ,disease and other conceivable socio political maladies.

Furthermore, this study will be of a good help to the Nigerian government, especially the present government to know the effectiveness of the external debt and economic growth polices implemented in the previous years and know exactly the next step to follow now in curtailing the total outstanding external debt because it is very obvious that the Nigeria external debt is now growing at alarming rate yearly. It must be added that this study is of relevance not only to Nigeria but to almost all the countries classified as LDCs especially as a result of various common features.

1.7 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study seeks to analyze Nigeria's external debt and its impact on her economic growth. In order to fully capture its effect on the economy, a thorough empirical investigation will be conducted with data covering a period of 36 years i.e. 1981-2017. This period was chosen to cover the period after the oil collapse and also the post debt-relief era.

1.8 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study is bound to be faced with limitations as other past research study have. Some of the prospect limitations of this study includes; firstly the challenge of sourcing for adequate data,

most times data are hardly seen from different institutions, internet, and libraries, even when. They are available most at times they are often inadequate, and this inadequacy can lead to false results of analysis.

Secondly another issue is that of time constraints. This is a major challenge in research works; due to this constraint certain grounds may not be covered.

However, despite these limitations, the research work still retains sufficient robustness and usefulness in analysing the impact of external debt on the economic growth of Nigeria.

1.9 STRUCTURE OF THE STUDY

This study is divided into five chapters.

Chapter 1 contains the general introduction which provides the background to the study, statement of problem, objectives of the study, research questions, research hypotheses, scope of the study, significance of study and limitation of the study. Chapter two examines the works of other economists on the subject matter of external debt and it consists of conceptual and definitional issues, theoretical, empirical and methodological review and a summary of literature. Chapter 3 provides the theoretical framework of the study and the methodology employed. It also contains the specification and estimation of the model.

Chapter four carries out a descriptive, trend and empirical analysis of the model estimated in chapter three.

Chapter five contains the summary, conclusion and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The 1950's and 1960's are most often described as the "golden years" for developing countries in economic development literature because of the rate of economic growth which was not just high but also internally generated. In the above years these LDC's increased their investment reliance on external resources however most of the growth in the 1970s was "debt led" and this led to persistent current account deficits with massive borrowings from the international money and capital market (ICM) to bridge payment gaps. External debt has increased steadily over the years in developing countries like Nigeria and as such, an analysis of the role external debt plays in economic growth and development is paramount. Aside from being an ardent booster of growth external debt has also been known to cause a number of problems for developing countries. The increases in external debt over the years in developing countries like

Nigeria has brought the issue of external debt out of hiding and has become a matter of concern both to the international and local community. Hence This need to constantly borrow as a means of financing has brought about an increasing literature among various economists.

2.1.1 Definition of external debt and economic growth

Arnane et al (2005) defines external debt as that portion of a country's debt that is acquired from foreign sources such as foreign corporations, government or financial institutions. According to (Ogbeifin, 2007), external debt arises as a result of the gap between domestic savings and investment. As the gap widens, debt accumulates and this makes the country to continually borrow increasing amounts in order to stay afloat. He further defined Nigeria's external debt as the debt owed by the public and private sectors of the Nigerian economy to non-residents and citizens that is payable in foreign currency, goods and services. It should be known that the act of borrowing creates debts according to Oyejide et al (1985).

Economic growth on the other hand, may be defined in terms of the total physical output or real income of an economy. Also it could be referred to as an increase in real output or per capital output of an economy. The definition correctly recognizes that the standard of living of

the people in any economy is best measured in terms of real output per person. The standard of living could decline in an economy if the population increased at a faster rate than the volume of the real output. It is therefore steady process by which the productive capacity of the economy is increased over time to bring about rising level of national income. Economic growth must be maintained if a nation is to improve the standard of living of the people.

For growth to take place that is for future output to be greater than the present output it is necessary to increase the existing level of productive capacity i.e. the available stock of capital goods. But this can happen only if part of current output is withheld from present consumption (i.e. saved) and used to add to the existing stock of capital goods is what is called investment .We can see therefore that growth is not possible without the savings investment process.

For the purpose of clarity some concepts related to external debt and economic growth will be defined and looked into, in order to avoid obscurity in the study.

- **The concept of Debt burden**

A debt burden is a large amount of money that one country or organization owes to another and which they find very difficult to repay. For countries the debt burden is the cost of servicing the public debt. Most of this debt burden is a really transfer from one generation to another. However, National debt can be a real debt burden because: If the debt is held externally. E.g. 25% of US debt is held abroad making US liable for external interest transfers. When debt is

held externally, it may also cause a depreciation in the exchange rate and hence a worsening of the terms of trade. (Imports more expensive) High public debt may also cause higher taxes which distort work incentives e.t.c.

- **The concept; Debt crisis**

This occurs when a country has accumulated a huge amount of debt such that it can no longer effectively manage the debt which leads to several mishaps in the domestic political economy. Mimiko (1997) defined debt crisis as a situation whereby a nation is severely indebted to external sources and is unable to repay the principal of the debt.

- **Deficit spending**

Deficit spending refers to the situation whereby government expenditure exceeds its receipts during a given financial year. The government incurs debts by spending more than it rose in revenue. These debts are called national or public debts which are defined as the cumulative total of various government indebtedness at any given moment. From the definition, one will note that government accumulates debts by running into deficit.

- **Debt overhang concept**

In the context of sovereign governments, the term refers to a situation in which the debt of a nation exceeds its future capacity to repay it. This can occur from an output gap or economic underemployment, repeatedly plugged by the creation of additional credit. A debt overhang can lead to stagnant growth and a degradation of living standards from reduced funds to spend in critical areas, such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure. Debt servicing is a contractually fixed charge on domestic real income and savings. As the size of debt grows, or as interest rate rises, debt service charge increases. Debt services payment is made is done only with the export earning, curtailed import, or with further external borrowing. Thus if the export earning diminishes, debt-service difficulties are likely to arise.

- **Debt sustainability concept**

Debt Sustainability is defined as the ability to maintain a constant debt-GDP ratio over a period of time. Sustainability is challenged when the debt to GDP ratio reaches an excessive value. Kasidi and Said thought that, a number of factors come into play when establishing if a country is able to service its debt. These factors include the existing debt stock and associated debt service, the prospective path of its deficits, the financing mix of the debt and the evolution of its repayment capacity in terms of foreign currency value of GDP, exports and government revenues.

- **The concept of External debt management**

External debt is the phenomenon used to describe the financial obligation that ties one party (debtor country) to another (lender country). External debt management is a strategy design to ensure that the debt stocks does not grow to an extent that the country can no longer conveniently service her debts and also that the terms are not enslaving. In other words, it is a mechanism where a nation's debt stock and the servicing arrangement (terms of loan) do not cause severe problems for the economy and society. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, external debt management involves an assessment of the country's capacity to service existing debts and a judgment on the desirability of contracting further loans. Therefore, External debt management in this work means a mechanism used by the responsible authority (Debt Management Board) to ensure that external debt does not affect its country in terms of investment, saving and capital generation which are the basis for economic growth and development, but should be bearable and/or productive.

2.1.2 Types of external debt

External debt includes almost every kind of money owed both publicly and privately within a nation's borders to governments, businesses and private individuals in other nations. Money borrowed by one government from another country's government, corporate stocks owned by foreign nationals and bills accrued by one country's citizens through doing business with a

foreign country all count as external debt. The only international foreign transactions excluded from external debt are financial derivative contracts and equity transactions.

2.1.3 Problems of external debt

The poor countries are faced not only with the problem of persistent balance of payments deficit but also of falling export earnings, low growth rate and lack of liquidity for financing their development programmes. The complex situation in which they are placed has landed them in the grips of international debt crisis of serious dimensions.

Any default on the part of some of these indebted countries is likely to engulf the entire international financial system in grave crisis or even collapse. Tejvan Pettinger October 22, 2016 state that the easiest guide to know when external debt becomes a problem is to look at the level of external debt to GDP. Although there are no precise rules for when external debt becomes a problem. But, a key factor is whether a country can satisfactorily meet debt interest payments from export earnings.

The IMF has suggested external debt should be kept below

1. A country's level of debt in Net Present Value to either 150 percent of exports or 250 percent of government.

2.1.4 Eternal debt and economic growth

The issue of external borrowing as a policy to promote economic growth creates serious debate among economists and policy makers. The main concern is whether or not external borrowing leads to economic growth in debtor countries. This debate results in two main perspectives for explaining the relationship between external debt and economic growth. On one hand, the Neoclassical and the Endogenous growth models advocated that there is a positive relationship between external debt and economic growth. They emphasized that debt is one of the sources for financing capital formation, and if financing capital formation through this means impact positively on investment, it could promote economic growth. On the other hand, among other scholars Krugman contradict this view by mentioning external debt as one of the factors hampering economic growth. Kalonji explained that heavy external debt is the cause of poverty in the debtors' country while Chongo noted that public debt is a double edged sword. This can also be seen in the mix opinion by Ojo and Sulaiman who examined the impact of external debt on the level of economic growth and the volume of investment in Nigeria and found that the current external debt ratio of GDP stimulate growth in the short-run, but the private investment which is a measure of real and tangible development shows a decline. Their opinion shows a mix result indicating a positive and negative relationship between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria. But given the ideology of the "growth-debt" nexus that a country should borrow abroad as long as the capital is inadequate and produces a rate of return that is higher than the cost of the foreign borrowing, it is generally expected that developing countries experiencing

inadequate capital will acquire external debt to supplement domestic savings and investment. The rates at which they borrow depend on the links among foreign and domestic savings, investment and economic growth so that the borrowing countries increase their capacity output with the aid of foreign savings. Nevertheless, external debt can only be productive if well managed by making the rate of return higher than the cost of servicing the debt.

However, the external debt profile of Nigeria has been on the increase and has constituted a source of concern about the future. Recently, the Nigerian government has embarked on borrowing externally for the main purpose of financing increased proportion of economic activities for economic growth. It has been argued by Ali and Mshelia that in Nigeria, external borrowing is often considered the best way out of embarrassing economic situations. Despite the seeming justification to borrow externally, it is soon discovered to become a perpetual lifeline burden, consequently engendering severe economic implications both to immediate and future generation economies, leaving Nigerians with an acute decline in the standard of living, high external dependence, gross social and economic overhead depreciation, currency depreciation, balance of payment disequilibria, exchange rate depreciation and rising inflationary rate. External Debt in Nigeria averaged 6375.33 Million USD from 2008 until 2015, reaching an all time high of 10718.43 Million USD in the fourth quarter of 2015. According to Nwankwo, the Nigerian external debt has risen to \$11 billion with debt sustainability ratio of 2.4% which is far below the sustainable ratio of 12.51 to the GDP.

2.1.5 Conditions for rapid economic growth in Nigeria

Economic growth is defined in terms of an increase in a nation's output of goods and services and measured by the gross domestic product (GDP).

Economic development encompasses growth, structural and institutional changes and the essential elements that make for a better quality in life such as education, health, nutrition and a better environment. Modern growth theory takes the view that capital, labour and entrepreneurship are essential for production to take place. However, economic growth is particularly the result of capital accumulation as it is generally accepted that more capital goods will be required if there is to be growth. If all gross investments are devoted to depreciation of capital thus merely keeping the existing capital stock intact, there will be no net investment and therefore no basis for economic growth with a given capital output ratio and a given perpetual maintained capital stock (zero net investment) output would be constant too. Only in so far as there is a net addition to capital stock that there will be growth. The essential ingredient for growth is therefore net investment or the excess of gross investment over depreciation. For, it is net investment alone (unless capital output ratio is changing) that can lead to economic growth. Although capital accumulation is basis to growth, there are some other complementary factors directly linked with capital formation for growth to take place. These factors include favourable economic environment, adequacy of infrastructure, security and political stability.

External debt is found to be a driver of economic growth if properly managed but its servicing rather than repayment is an inhibiting factor to economic growth.

2.2 REVIEW OF THEORETICAL LITERATURE

Several theoretical contributions have been made as regards the subject matter of external debt and economic growth. These theories are of relevance to this study as they serve as a building block to this research work.

2.2.1 External debt and economic theory

The matter of external debt has become a major impediment to the growth and stability of developing countries. Economists have therefore chosen to explore the channels through which the effects of external debt burden are realized and have come up with two competing theories namely the debt overhang theory and the crowding-out effect theory. Debt-overhang occurs when a nation's debt is more than its debt repayment ability. Krugman (1982) explains debt overhang as one whereby the expected repayment amount of debt exceeds the actual amount at which it was contracted. Borensztein (1990) also defined debt overhang as one where the debtor nation benefits very little from the returns on additional investment due to huge debt service obligations. The "debt overhang

effect” comes into play when accumulated debt stock discourages investors from investing in the private sector for fear of heavy tax placed on them by government. This is known as tax disincentive. The tax disincentive here implies that because of the high debt and as such huge debt service payments, it is assumed that any future income accrued to potential investors would be taxed heavily by government so as to reduce the amount of debt service and this scares off the investors thereby leading to disinvestment in the overall economy and as such a fall in the rate of growth (Ayadi and Ayadi, 2008). In addition, Clement et al (2003) stated that external debt accumulation can promote investment up to a certain point where debt overhang sets in and the willingness of investors to provide capital starts to deteriorate. Audu (2004) relates the concept of debt overhang to Nigeria’s debt situation. He stated that the debt service burden has prevented rapid growth and development and has worsened the social issues. Nigeria’s expected debt service is seen to be increasing function of her output and as such resources that are to be used for developing the economy are indirectly taxed away by foreign creditors in form of debt service payments (Ekperiware et al, 2005). This has further increased uncertainty in the Nigerian economy which discourages foreign investors and also reduces the level of private investment in the economy. Cohen (1993) and Clement et al (2003) observe that aside from the effect of high debt stock on investment, external debt can also affect growth through accumulated debt service payments which are likely to “crowd

out” investment (private or public) in the economy. The crowding-out effect refers to a situation whereby a nation’s revenue which is obtained from foreign exchange earnings is used to pay up debt service payments. This limits the resources available for use for the domestic economy as most of it is soaked up by external debt service burden which reduces the level of investment. Tayo (1993) opined that the impact of debt servicing of growth is damaging as a result of debt-induced liquidity constraints which reduces government expenditure in the economy. These liquidity constraints arise as a result of debt service requirements which shift the focus from developing the domestic economy to repayments of the debt. Public expenditure on social infrastructure is reduced substantially and this affects the level of public investment in the economy. Furthermore, some researchers have come up with other ways through which external debt may affect economic growth. According to (Borenstein, 1990) external debt affects growth through the credit rationing effect which is a condition faced by countries that are unable to contract new loans based on their previous inability to pay.

2.2.2 The debt overhang theory

According to Krugman (1988), the debt overhang theory shows that if there is some likelihood that in the future debt will be larger than the country's repayment ability; expected debt-service costs will discourage further domestic and foreign investment because the expected

rate of return from the productive investment projects will be very low to support the economy as the significant portion of any subsequent economic progress will accrue to the creditor country. This eventually will further reduce both domestic and foreign investments and hence downsizes economic growth (Krugman, 1988, Sachs, 1989a).

Claessens and Diwan (1990) argue that "debt overhang is a situation in which the illiquidity effect, the disincentive effect, or both effects are strong enough to discourage growth in the absence of concessions by creditors". This is a "narrow" definition of the debt overhang where the impact of a high external debt that is linked to the tax disincentives argument, where any success in indebted country's economic performance is taxed away by creditors and ultimately little is left over for domestic investment and subsequent growth (Hjertholm, 2001).

According to Were (2001) debt overhang is much wider in that the effects of debt do not only affect investment in physical capital but any activity that involves incurring costs up-front for the sake of increased output in the future. Such activities include investment in human capital (in terms of education and health) and in technology acquisition whose effects on growth may be even stronger over time.

Essentially the higher the stock of debt to the country, the higher is the current sacrifice for the sake of the future growth. The theory of debt overhang is well explained by the hypothesis of Debt Laffer curve which relates the magnitude of country's debt and the value of repayment.

According to Freytag et al (2008) the NPV of the debt repayments increases with stock of debt up to a certain threshold point beyond which a higher face value of the debt will be associated with lower efforts and investments, lower economic growth and lower NPV of expected debt service.

According to Clements et al (2005) high levels of debt can depress economic growth in low-income countries, external debt slows growth only after its face value reaches a threshold level estimated to be about 50 percent of GDP (or, in net present value terms, 20-25 percent of GDP). Debt overhang depresses growth by increasing private investor's uncertainty about governmental action taken to meet the debt service obligations. These include increase in money supply that causes inflation, distortion of future tax policies (Clements et al, 2005). Therefore the debt overhang problem is linked to the transfer of resources from capital scarce to capital surplus countries.

The debt Laffer curve argument (which was apparently introduced by Jeffrey Sachs) is derived from the tax laffer curve hypothesis introduced by Arthur Laffer (1981), who argues that if personal tax rates were raised, they generate a dreadful impact on government tax revenue. The reason is that high tax rates either simply discourages investment or leads to tax evasion. Figure 1 presents the Debt Laffer Curve of external debt, expected payments and amortizations.

Figure 2.1

Chart 3

Debt thresholds

Debt has an inverted-U relationship with growth. The effect is initially positive, but as debt ratios increase beyond point A, debt eventually slows growth. When debt reaches point B, the overall contribution of debt turns negative.

Source: Authors.

If the stock of external debt is small, such that from the origin to point 'A', then it is expected that the debtor country will be able to meet the forthcoming debt repayment in full without a problem. Under this situation the marginal expected debt repayment with relation to the debt stock is one. However, after this point the expected debt repayment expands at a lower rate in relation to the debt accumulation. A country under this level of debt stock is expected to have some difficulties in meeting the debt repayment; this can be seen from the marginal expected debt repayment of between 0 and 1 exclusive. The risk of inability to service the debt increases with the increase in debt stock. The risk may vary from country to country according to the level of their debt's interest rate.

At point B, the expected debt repayment reaches its maximum saturated point and then starts falling, at this point and beyond the marginal impact of debt is negative. A country under this situation is totally unable to service the debts and most of the time declared to be in debt crisis.

On extending the debt laffer curve to show the contribution of external debt on economic growth on a country we can have figure 2 below.

Figure 2.2

This posits that larger debt stocks tend to be associated with lower probabilities of debt repayment. On the upward-sloping or “good” section of the curve, increases in the face value of debt are associated with increases in debt repayment, while increases in expected debt repayment on the down-ward sloping or “bad” section of the curve. This shows the non linear relationship of external debt and economic growth as supported by Pattillo et al (2002). A reasonable level of

external debt actually has a positive impact on economic growth while excessive debt stock is destructive. As debt stock increases with time growth decreases and it can sometimes reach a negative level of economic growth.

Combining the two figures we have figure 3. Here we can see that as debt increases, creditors' expectations of being paid are distorted. From the figure it is easily seen that when the expected payment of the debt increases proportionally less than the debt stock, the distortions are such that extra amounts of debt start decelerating the GDP growth rate. Moreover, if the debt accumulation achieves higher levels such that the debtor starts diminishing or failing to make its regular amortizations, any extra debt increment will be translated into negative contributions to the GDP growth rate.

Figure 2.3

Chart 1

High debt hobbles growth

Growth drops during the buildup of debt in the 1980s, and it rises during the reduction of debt in the 1990s.

Source: Authors.

Note: The sample consists of 93 developing countries. Data consist of three-year moving averages over the 1972–1998 period (data points for midyear). Two observations for Yemen, an extreme outlier with respect to the debt-to-exports variable, were dropped for the computation of sample means.

2.2.3 The dual gap theory

Omoruyi (2005) stated that most economies have experienced a shortfall in trying to bridge the gap between the level of savings and investment and have resorted to external Borrowing in order to fill this gap. This gap provides the motive behind external debt as pointed out by (Chenery, 1966) which is to fulfill the lack of savings and investment in a nation as increases in savings and investment would vis-à-vis lead to a rise in economic growth (Hunt, 2007). The dual-gap analysis is provides a framework

that shows that the development of any nation is a function of investment and that such investment requires domestic savings which is not sufficient to ensure that development take place (Oloyede, 2002). The dual-gap theory is coined from a national income accounting identity which connotes that excess investment expenditure (investment-savings gap) is equivalent to the surplus of imports over exports (foreign exchange gap).

2.2.4 Crowding effect

Claessens et al, (1996) stressed out that, the other channels through which the service of a large amount of external debt obligations can affect economic performance include the 'crowding out' effect, the lack of access to international financial markets and the effects of the stock of debt on the general level of uncertainty in the economy.

The crowding out effect occurs when there is a reduction in the current debt service that lead to an increase in current investment for any given level of future indebtedness (Cohen, 1993). If a greater portion of export revenue is used to service external debt, very little is available for investment and growth. Claessens et al (1996) also argues that where foreign assistance is related to the debt and debt service of indebted poor countries, the effects of a debt overhang on economic performance is a more complex question. Debt servicing difficulties lead to a deterioration of relations with creditors, thus reducing the amount of finance indebted poor countries can access (Khan and Villaneuva, 1991).

2.2.5 Dependency theory

The dependency theory seeks to outline the factors that have contributed to the development of the underdeveloped countries. This theory is based on the assumption that resources flow from a “periphery” of poor and underdeveloped states to a “core” of wealthy states thereby enriching the latter at the expense of the former. The phenomenon associated with the dependency theory is that poor states are impoverished while rich ones are enriched by the way poor states are integrated into the world system (Todaro, 2003; Amin, 1976). Dependency theory states that the poverty of the countries in the periphery is not because they are not integrated or fully integrated into the world system as is often argued by free market economists, but because of how they are integrated into the system. From this standpoint a common school of thought is the bourgeoisie scholars. To them the state of underdevelopment and the constant dependence of less developed countries on developed countries is as a result of their domestic mishaps. They believe this issue can be explained by their lack of close integration, diffusion of capital, low level of technology, poor institutional framework, bad leadership, corruption, mismanagement, etc. (Momoh and Hundeyin, 1999). They see the under-development and dependency of the third world countries as being internally inflicted rather than externally afflicted. To this school of thought, a way out of the problem is for third world countries to seek foreign assistance in terms of aid, loan, investment, etc, and allow

undisrupted operations of the Multinational Corporations (MNCs). Due to the underdeveloped nature of most LDC's, they are dependent on the developed nations for virtually everything ranging from technology, aid, technical assistance, to culture, etc. The dependent position of most underdeveloped countries has made them vulnerable to the products of the Western metropolitan countries and Breton Woods institutions (Ajayi, 2000). The dependency theory gives a detailed account of the factors responsible for the position of the developing countries and their constant and continuous reliance on external for their economic growth and development.

2.2.6 The Solow growth model and external debt

The Solow-growth model was published in 1956 as a seminar paper on economic growth and development under the title, "A contribution to the theory of economic growth". Like most economic growth theories, Solow growth model is built upon some assumptions:

- i. Countries will produce and consume only a single homogenous good.
- ii. Technology is exogenous in the short run. The Solow growth model is developed based on a Cobb - Douglas production function given by the form:

$$Y = F(K, L) = K^\alpha L^{1-\alpha}$$

Where $Y =$ output

$K =$ Capital input

$L =$ Labor input

α and $1-\alpha$ are output elasticities of capital and labor respectively and α is a number between 0 and 1.

The other important equation from the Solow growth model is the capital accumulation equation expressed in the form:

$$\dot{K} = sY - dK$$

Where: $\dot{K} =$ change in capital stock

$sY =$ gross investment

$dK =$ depreciation during the production process With mathematical manipulation

Solow derives the capital accumulation equation in terms of per worker i.e.

$$\dot{k} = sy - (n+d)k .$$

This implies that the change in capital per worker is a function of investment per worker, depreciation per worker and population growth. Of these three variables only investment per worker is positively related with change in capital per worker.

Solow Growth Model and External Debt

The Solow growth model is built on a closed economy which makes use of labour and capital as its means of production. Under this scenario the implication of external debt on growth can be seen through its effect on the domestic saving which in turn used as investment in a closed model. The general effect of external debt on the Solow growth model can be analyzed by looking at the individual effects of the debt overhang and debt crowding theories on the Solow growth model. According to the debt overhang hypothesis, the government in an attempt to amortize the accumulated debt, will increase tax rate on the private sector (as means of transferring resources to the public sector). This will discourage private sector investment and also reduce government expenditure on infrastructure as the resources are used to pay up huge debt service payments instead of being put into good use. This will lead to a reduction of total (private and public) investment in the economy and a shift downward of both the investment and production function curves in Solow growth model. On the other hand in the case of debt crowding out, in a bid to clear their outstanding debts use their revenue

from export earnings and in some cases transfer resources including foreign aid and foreign exchange resources to service their forthcoming debt. Those countries which transfer revenue from export earnings which can be used in investment in the economy to avoid huge debt payments will discourage public investment. This in turn will decrease economic growth and will shift both the investment and production function curves in Solow growth model downward (Dereje, 2013).

2.2.7 The classical theory of economic growth

The basic theme of the classical model was the development of the economy from a progressive state into a stationary state. However, “the ultimate arrival, at which wages would have reached a minimum acceptable level and net investment would have ceased because of low profits, could be postponed indefinitely by a stream of highly productive inventions.”

The classical theory is basically a synthesis of the doctrines put forward by Adam Smith, T. R. Malthus, David Ricardo, J. S Mill and others.

The following classical propositions are worth mentioning in this connection:

1. According to the classicists, one central feature of the progressive state was a high level of accumulation, which permitted an increase in the output of the community by raising labour

productivity (as also that of land) by adding to the productive resources available. The rate of accumulation basically depended on the level of profit.

2. Total profits depended on two primary factors: the total product of labour, and the level of wages. As a corollary, it also depended on the marginal productivity of labour.

3. The productivity of labour depended on the stock of capital as also the technique employed.

4. In the short run actual or market wages could lie above the subsistence level which would warrant an increase in population. But in the long run, due to population growth, wages tended to approach the subsistence level. And, as a result, population growth would come to a halt.

The classical model may be summed up in terms of the basic Baumol- diagram. To start with, we assume that in the early stage of the classical economy population is small compared to natural resources. Consequently, profits the rate of accumulation, and thus wages are all relatively high. It is also assumed that population adjusts itself relatively quickly to a change in the level of market wages (the wages actually paid in practice).

2.2.8 Neo-classical theory of economic growth

The work of economists Tobin, Swan, Solow, Meade, Phelps and Johnson is termed as neo-classical theory of economic growth. The assumptions adopted by these theorists in the

neo-classical theory are based on the views and norms given by neo- classical economists, such as Alfred Marshall, Wicksell, and Pigou.

Following are some of the assumptions of the neo-classical theory:

- a. Assuming perfect competition in commodity as well as factor markets
- b. Making factor payments equal to the marginal revenue productivity
- c. Maintaining a variable ratio between capital and output
- d. Assuming full employment condition

The assumptions of the neo-classical theory would be clearer by comparing them with the assumptions of the Harrod-Domar model.

According to the neo-classical theory, the economic growth is determined with the help of certain factors, such as stock of capital, supply of labor, and technological development over time.

The production function for the neo-classical theory can be expressed as follows:

$$Y = F (K, L, T)$$

Where, Y = National output

K = Capital stock

L = Labor supply

T = Scale of technological development

According to the assumption of constant return to scale, increase in national output (ΔY) would be equal to the marginal productivity (MP) times ΔK and ΔL . Therefore,

$$\Delta Y = \Delta K \cdot MP + \Delta L \cdot MP$$

Where, MP = marginal physical product of capital

MP = marginal physical product of capital

When the equation of increase in national output is divided by Y, then we get the following equation:

$$\Delta Y/Y = \Delta K (MP /Y) + \Delta L (MP /Y)$$

The first term in the R.H.S is multiplied by K/K and second term by L/L; the resultant equation would be as follows:

$$\Delta Y/Y = \Delta K/Y (K \cdot MP /Y) + \Delta L/Y (L \cdot MP /Y)$$

The K. MP and L. MP represent the total stake of capital and labor in the national output, whereas K/Y^* MP and L/Y^* MP represent the relative stake of capital and labor in the national output. Therefore,

$$(K.MP/Y) + (L.MP /Y) = 1$$

Let us assume that $(K.MP /Y) = b$, then

$$(L.MP /Y) = 1-b$$

Putting the value of $(K.MP /Y)$ and $(L.MP /Y)$ in the following equation, we get:

$$\Delta Y/Y = \Delta K/Y (K.MP /Y) + \Delta L/Y (L.MP /Y)$$

$$\Delta Y/Y = b \Delta K/K + (1 - b) \Delta T/T$$

In the preceding equation, the values of b and $1- b$ represents the elasticity of output with reference to the capital and labor respectively.

Therefore, according to the neo-classical theory, the economic growth rate is represented as follows:

Economic growth (at a given level of technology) = Elasticity of output with reference to the increase in capital stock + Elasticity of output with reference to the increase in labor

However, in case of technological change, the change in national output can be represented as follows:

$$\Delta Y/Y = b \Delta K/K + (1 - b) \Delta T/T$$

Therefore, in case of technological development, the economic growth rate can be represented as follows:

Economic growth (at a given level of technology) = Elasticity of output with reference to the increase in capital stock + Elasticity of output with reference to the increase in technological progress.

Some of the limitations of the neo-classical theory are as follows:

- a. Regards technology as a constant factor, which is not true. This is due to the fact that a technology keeps advancing with time
- b. Considers factor prices as the major factor for determining economic growth. However, the adjustments of factor prices can be interrupted with a change in liquidity.
- c. Does not include the investment functions; therefore, the neo-classical theory has failed to describe the expectations of entrepreneurs and capital accumulation by them.
- d. Considers capital assets as homogeneous, which is not real.

2.2.9 The Lewis theory of economic growth

The Lewis (1954) model was the first model to explicitly focus on dualistic economic development. The original Lewis model was simple yet genius with the clarity he expressed his ideas; (Chen and Mehlenbacher) nearly every model is some way related to the roots of the Lewis model. The Lewis model understood that in the most LCD's most workers are in the rural/agricultural sector. These sectors in these nations are not endowed with capital with high productivity like agricultural sectors in the developed nations.

The Lewis models abandoned the traditional assumptions of labour and capital equilibria. The Lewis model assumes that the rural sector (agriculture) is very primitive; it is labour intensive, with little or capital endowment leading to subsistence agriculture. The urban sector (modern/industrialized) is capital driven with much higher standards of living than the rural sector. Hence this defines Lewis' dualistic economy.

The 'labour surplus' concept implies those workers in agricultural sector with zero marginal productivity. This implies that they can be taken out of the rural sector without reduction in agricultural output.

The assumptions following this model are that:

I. Non-surplus labourers are working in full capacity.

II. There are no capitalist farmers paying rent to Landlords and of capitalist farmers in rural sector.

The model however proposes that with holding surplus labourers from the rural sector and sending them to urban sector will not lead to decrease in agricultural goods and urban goods. He however concluded that the consistent driver of growth is technological advancement, not manipulative of relative prices.

2.2.10 The Endogenous Growth Theory

The basic improvement of endogenous growth theory over the previous models is that it explicitly tries to model technology (i.e, it looks into the determinants of technology) rather than assuming to be exogenous (Verbeck, 2000).

Mostly, economic growth comes from technological progress which is essentially the ability of an economic organization to utilize its process of learning to operate newly created production facilities in a more productive way or more generally from learning to cope with regard to changes in the structure of production which industrial progress must imply. (Verbeck, 2000).

According traditional growth theories, there is no intrinsic characteristic of economies that causes them to grow over extended period of time. They however emphasized growth with the absence of “shocks” (government intervention).

The new theory, according to Todaro and Smith (2011), provides a theoretical framework for analyzing endogenous growth, this persistent growth in GNP which is determined by the system governing the production process rather than forces outside the system. According to the theory, the potentially high rates of return on investment offered by developing countries with low capital-labour ratios are greatly eroded by lower levels of complementary investment in human capital (education), infrastructure or research and development (R and D) (Todaro and Smith, 2011). This position supports that the endogenous growth suggests an active role for public policy in promoting economic growth and development through direct and indirect investment in human capital.

2.3 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

The motive behind external debt is to boost economic growth and development of any nation but as a result of future high debt service payments, it poses a serious threat to the economy of that nation. Economic researchers have therefore sought out to investigate the implication of external debt burden on the economies of debtor nations and have come up with diverse views.

In a comparative study conducted by Ayadi and Ayadi (2008) on the impact of external debt on economic growth of Nigeria and South African using both Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Generalized Least Square (GLS), they found evidence for a

negative relationship between external debt and economic growth in both countries. However, South African is better than Nigeria in managing her debt service. In addition, external debt contributes positively to growth up to a point after which its contribution becomes negative in Nigeria (reflecting the presence of non-linearity effects).

Adesola (2009) examine the relationship between debt servicing and economic growth in Nigeria, using the ordinary least square multiple regression approach. His result showed that debt payments to the London club creditors, Paris club creditors, Promissory notes holders and other creditors have significant impact on the GDP and GFCF (Gross Fixed Capital Formation), while debt payments to Paris club and debt payment to Promissory notes holders are positively related to GFCF and GDP, the debt payments to London club creditors and other creditors revealed a negative effect on GFCF and GDP for the period of 1981-2004.

Akram (2010) in the study of the impact of public debt on economic growth and investment in Pakistan developed a hybrid model that explicitly incorporates the role of public debt in growth equations. He adopted the Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique in estimating the model and the result revealed that both domestic and external debt have negative relationship with per capita GDP and investment, confirming the existence of "Debt overhang effect" which crowds out private investment.

Safdari and Mehirizi (2011) investigated the effect of external debt on economic growth in Iran for the period of 1974-2007, by observing the balance and long term relation of five variables: GDP, Private investment, Public Investment, external debt and Imports. They employed the Vector autoregressive model (VAR) in their econometric analysis and the result of the research showed that external debt and imports had a negative effect on gross domestic product, but variables of private and public investments had positive effects on economic growth.

In a related study conducted by Amassoma (2011) investigating the causal nexus between external debt, internal debt, and economic growth in Nigeria, employed the Granger causality test in determining the direction of causality of the variables. He found that there exist a bidirectional causal relationship between internal debt and economic growth, while external debt and economic growth have a unidirectional causal relationship suggesting that economic growth causes external debt in Nigeria.

Kabadayi et al (2012) determine the impact of external debt on economic growth in 19 Transitional economies adopting the panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. It was found that external debt has positive impact on economic growth, also openness of the economy has a positive impact in the long run, while external debt to

export ratio has a negative impact on growth rate of the transitional economies in the short run.

Egbetunde (2012) in his study of causal relations tested for the stationary properties of variables and found them stationary at first difference, the result of the co-integration test showed the presence of long run relationship between Public debt and economic growth in Nigeria. The result of the study revealed that there exist a bi-directional relationship between public debt and economic growth, implying that improvement in economic activities call for borrowing to enhance on-going development processes in the economy, and borrowing also promotes growth in Nigeria. Similarly Rahman et al (2012) in their study of relationship between external debt and gross domestic product in Bangladesh used annual time series data to avoid seasonal biases, the ADF and Phillips-Perron test were carried out to ascertain the stationary properties of the variables, Granger causality and co-integration models were also employed to determine the Long run relationship as well as the direction of causality that exists between the variables, they found that there exist a bi-directional causal relationship between GDP and external debt.

Sulaiman and Azeez (2012) investigated the impact of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria using GDP as the dependent variable while ratio of external debt to

export, inflation and exchange rate were used as the independent variables. Annual time series data covering the period of 1970 to 2010 were used, which were analyzed using the ordinary least square technique, ADF, unit root test, Johansen co-integration test and Error correction model (ECM). Results from the study showed that external debt has a positive impact on the Nigerian economy in the long run. They therefore recommended that external borrowing should be obtained for economic growth reasons rather than social and political motives.

Barik (2012) researched on the indirect relationship between government debt and economic growth in India for the period of 1981-2011. He conducted an econometric analysis with an augmented Solow (1956) Neoclassical growth model, and found that there exists an indirect relationship between public debt and economic growth in India. The result of the study reveals that public debt appears to be positively related to both investment and output growth and thereby has an indirect impact on economic growth through its positive effect on investment.

In the empirical research by Ishola et al (2013), on the effect of external debt on sustainable economic growth in Nigeria for the period of 1980-2010, using the ordinary least Square regression method, the study found that a 12.3 percent change in economic growth is as a result of external debt and prime lending rate in Nigeria. It therefore

recommends that the government should through an act of its political will address the fundamental causes of external debt and also ensure adequate utilization of borrowed funds to develop the different sectors of the economy so as to enhance the economic growth of the nation.

Babu et al (2014) estimate the effect of external debt as a share of GDP in economic growth in East Africa Community (EAC). Using annual data from 1970-2010, the study employs a panel fixed-effects model which was based on the Solow growth model augmented for debt. The findings suggest a negative significant effect of external debt on GDP per capita growth rate. Reduction of external debt burden was therefore recommended to promote rapid economic growth.

Ibi and Aganyi (2015) analyse the impact of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria. The variance decomposition and impulse response from Vector Auto-Regression (VAR) was the econometric technique employed to test whether or not External Debt, Ratio of External debt to Exports and other economic control variables stimulate economic growth. Based on the two-stage data processing, the result reveals a weak causation between external debt and economic growth in the Nigerian context. This implies that external debt could not be used to forecast improvement or slowdown in economic growth in Nigeria.

In an attempt to ascertain the impact of external debt on economic growth of Nigeria, Nwannebuike et al (2016) adopted the Ex-post facto research design. Data were analysed using Ordinary Least Square method and diagnostic tests were conducted using Augmented Dick Fuller Unit Root Test, Co-integration and Error Correction Model. The result of the study revealed that External Debt is positively related to GDP in the short run but a negative relationship at long run. Also a negative relationship was established between debt service stock and GDP while Exchange Rate had a positive relationship with GDP. The study recommended that the Debt Management Office should ensure that loans were utilized for purposes for which they were acquired and also a limit for borrowing should be set for states and federal governments based on well-defined criteria.

From the foregoing it is evident that the literature on external debt and economic growth is replete with its divergent results. While Kabadayi et al (2011), Sulaiman and Azeez (2012), Barik (2012) and Nwannebuike et al (2016) found evidence for a positive relationship between external debt and growth, Ayadi and Ayadi (2008), Akram (2010), Safdari and Mehirizi (2011) and Babu et al (2014) found evidence for a negative relationship. Similarly, Egbetunde (2012) and Rahman et al (2012), found that there exists bi-directional relationship between external debt and economic growth, Amassoma (2011) found a unidirectional causal relationship between external debt and economic growth. The divergence observed in these results suggests differences in theoretical and

methodological approaches. The nature of the relationship between external debt and economic growth in the Nigerian context is subject to empirical investigation, such enquiry is what this study is set to achieve and to find out if this study will corroborate any of the above outcomes.

Following the research works done by many researchers, there were certain limitations to their findings. Given UTOMI (2014), the effect of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria. From 1980 to 2012, he use the Johansen co-integration test, to test the short run relationship between external debt and economic growth. The researcher faced challenges in acquiring secondary data on some variables for Nigeria and as such these variables were exempted from the model. Some researchers also encounter certain limitations in analysing external debt impact on economic growth in Nigeria. This study, in order to avoid certain limitations faced by previous researchers, adopts The Ordinary least square method of estimation will be used as it depicts long run economic growth and Error correction model . Also the study will make use of secondary data covering a period of 36 years i.e. 1981 – 2016.

2.4 EXTERNAL DEBT POLICY IN NIGERIA

Issues analyzed here include; the history of Nigeria's external debt causes of these debts in details, their sources and finally an Analysis of the Nigerian external debt management policies and performance.

2.4.1 History of Nigeria external debt

Nigeria's external indebtedness can be traced back to the pre-independence period when in 1958 a loan of US\$28 million dollars was contracted from the World Bank for railway construction. This debt did not pose a serious burden reason being that it was acquired on soft terms i.e. with no interest or below market rate of interest. After this period, the need for external aid was relatively low until in 1977/1978 when there was a fall in world oil prices which in turn reduced the nation's oil receipts. Before this period Nigeria was experiencing abundance in oil receipts especially with the oil boom of 1973-1976. After crude oil was first discovered in 1956, it became a major source of foreign exchange earnings as there was a gradual drift from agriculture which had been the dominant provider of export earnings, employment e.t.c to near total dependence on oil as the mainstay of the economy. Following the fall in oil prices, it became necessary for the government to correct balance of payment difficulties and finance projects. This led to the first major borrowing of US\$1 billion which is referred to as the JUMBO LOAN in 1978 from the international capital market (ICM). Although this loan was used to

finance various medium and long term infrastructural projects, the returns obtained from these projects were not enough to amortize the nation's debts as many of the projects as included in the Fourth National Development Plans (1981-1985) involved mainly the use of imported materials. In 1979, there was a recovery in the oil market and oil was sold in Nigeria at US\$39.00 per barrel which led to the belief that the economy was bouncing back. But due to the fact that there was excessive importation, it resulted in over-invoicing of imports and under-invoicing of exports and in 1982 when there was another collapse in world oil prices it caused severe strains and stresses on the economy. Foreign exchange was declining rapidly and there were large amount of deficits in government financing. In the face of drastic oil downturn and dwindling oil reserves, the rate of borrowings increased from the international capital market (ICM). At this point the nation's debt profile had begun rising astronomically due to the increasing external debt service payments. In 1980 external debt stood at US\$8.5 billion and by 1985 it nearly reached US\$19 billion showing an increase of about 45.02%. The increasing in debt service payments interests resulted in mounting of trade debts arrears. By 1997 the nation's debt stock stood at US\$27.0878 billion; US\$18.9804 billion Paris Club debt; US\$4.3727 billion Multilateral debt; \$1.6125 billion Promissory notes and US\$0.7919 billion Non Paris Bilateral debt (Ministry of Finance, 1997). Due to the rise in external debt there was a corresponding increase in external debt servicing ratios; debt/GDP and

debt/export earnings. As at December 31st 2001, the external debt stock stood at US\$28.35 billion which was about 59.4% of GDP and 153.9% of export earnings.

2.4.2 Causes of federal external debt

According to the Central Bank Of Nigeria brief series, the major factor that contributed to the increased size of Nigeria external debt crisis include the rapid growth of public expenditure, particularly the expenditure on capital projects, borrowing from the international community on non concessional interest rate, decline in oil earnings for the late 1970's and the emergence of trade arrears.

- i. The cause of Nigeria's external debt according to Aluko and Arowolo (2010) are;
- ii. Inefficient trade and exchange rate policies
- iii. Adverse exchange rate movement
- iv. Adverse interested rate movement
- v. Poor lending and inefficient loan utilization
- vi. Poor debt management practices and accumulation of arrears and penalties

Other cause of Nigeria external debt burden as given by Nigeria debt management office website was reckless and inefficient borrowing which include;

- i. Massive external borrowing in 1980's to offset the collapse in oil prices
- ii. Borrowing not linked to future growth or exports
- iii. Insufficient regard given to economic viability of projects
- iv. Poor Implementation due to weak absorptive capacity and government problems
- v. Mismatch between long-term and project profiles
- vi. Leakages associated with governance problems
- vii. Interest rate risk as LIBOR rates escalated

Research has it that the policies adopted during decades of the 1970's and 80's led to structural changes which made Nigeria economy vulnerable to external shocks.

2.4.3 Sources of external debt

Nigeria has two major categories of external creditors; official and private creditors. Her official creditors include the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), African Development Fund (ADF), the International Bank for reconstruction and development (IBRD), the African Development Bank (AFDB), Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) fund and the European Investment Bank. The above listed are Nigeria's multilateral creditors which also include the World bank and

International Monetary Fund (IMF) which were very active lenders in the 1970s/1980s. The bilateral creditors include the Paris Club and Non-Paris Club creditors. The Paris Club is an informal group of official creditors which was created to aid debtor countries going through payment difficulties by finding sustainable and lasting solutions. Also part of Nigeria's debt profile are private creditors which are made up of promissory note holders and the London Club group. The total debt outstanding as at 31st December 2004 stood at US\$35.94 billion with Paris Club (85.82%), multilateral creditors (7.86%), London Club (4.01%), Non-Paris Club (0.13%) and Promissory notes (2.18%) (DMO, 2012). This clearly that the largest proportion of Nigeria's external debt is accrued to the Paris Club group of creditors.

The Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (1999, 2003), shows the source of Nigeria's external debt outstanding from 1970 to 2003. During the period of 1970 to 1977, the official creditors were the only source of external borrowing and hence, it accounted for all Nigeria's external debt burden. Up to the mid 1970's multilateral debt was more important. However, between the late 1970's and the late 1980's the London club which includes the market capital loans formed the largest component. For instance, in 1979 London club debt represented almost 64% of the external debt stock. While private debt represented 83% of foreign debt outstanding in 1982. This was the case of 1984. But 1985 through 1990's and upward, the official debt

became the major source of Nigeria's external debt accounting for over 90% of Nigeria's external debt while private creditors accounted for a paltry of 7% of Nigeria external debt.

2.4.4 External debt management strategies in Nigeria

The management of external debt became a major responsibility for the Central Bank in the 1980 which necessitated an established of Department in collaboration with the federal Ministry of Finance for the management of external debt, for better management of Nigeria's external debt, the debt management office was created in 2000 which work with the government transformation agenda. The Debt Management office (DMO) has made Great stride in debt management by restoring Nigeria's external credibility. Record has it that prior to the end of 1990 Nigeria faced major economic challenges ranging from the mismanagement of oil revenues to poor external debt management. The oil revenue which were suppose to propel the growth of the economy became a source of political, economic and social distortions. Hence Nigeria's external image was punctured, economic management was in chaos, and external borrowing grossly mismanaged.

External debt management refers to a complete institutional and technical arrangements involved in organizing external liabilities of a country so that the debt service burden is kept at a sustainable level (Ajayi, 2001). A country's debt level is sustainable if the country is expected to meet current and future external debt-service obligations Emilian and Emilia (2007) in full.

According to Ojo, external debt management may be defined as strategy which seeks to alter the stock, composition structure and terms of debt with a view of maintaining at any time sustainable level of debt service payment. External debt management has become an important issue in developing countries. It implies the planned acquisition, deployment and retirement of external loans drawn either for development purposes or for balance of payments acquisition. In the 1980, the management of the external debt became major responsibility of the central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). This necessitated the establishment (setting up) of a Department in collaboration with Federal Ministry of Finance to the management of external debt. Although the debt management strategies and measures varied from time to time since the government over the years adopted the under listed strategies and measures to deal with the debt problem. They include:

1. Embargo on new Loans and Directives to State Government to restrict external borrowing to the barest minimum. The embargo was to check the escalation of total debt stock and minimize additional debt burden. However, these have not been particularly effective as indiscriminate quest for external loans have not been adopted. Although rescheduling has conferred short term relief or debt service obligations, the debt over-hang has however hardly be abated as the
2. Limit on debt service payments: This requires setting aside portion of export earnings to allow for internal development.

3. Debt Restructuring: This involve the reduction in the burden of an existing debt through refinancing, rescheduling bring back, issuance of collateralized bonds and the provision of new money. The Federal Government in year 2001 established a semi – autonomous debt management office under the Presidency. The creation of DMO (Debt Management Office) consolidated the debt management functions in a single agency, ensuring proper coordination of the Country’s debt recording and management activities, including debt service forecast, debt service repayments, and advising on debt negotiation as well as new borrowings. Debt stock has continued to increase significantly. Debt restructuring policy involves the reduction in the burden of an existing debt through refinancing, rescheduling, and buy-back insurance of collateralized bonds and provision of new money. A refinancing arrangement means the procurement of a loan by a debtor to pay off an existing debt, particularly short term-trade debt so as to ease the debt burden. It should be noted that the first refinancing arrangement by Nigeria was made in July 1983, followed by second arrangements in September of the same year. In both agreements,\$2.1 billion worth of trade arrears was refinanced. The rescheduling of debt involved changing maturing, tenure and terms of debt structure. For instance in 1986, debt worth \$1.6 billion due to London club and payable in 1987 was rescheduled to extend to 1996 with four years grace period. Furthermore, the payback arrangement which implied the offer of a substantial discount to pay off existing debts was concluded on 21st January, 1982 when Nigeria bought 6.2% (\$3.395 billion) commercial debt owed to the London club at 60% discount.

Debt conversion programme was made to complement other strategies of debt management. In Nigeria, debt conversion exercise involved the sale of an external debt instrument for a domestic debt or equity participation in domestic enterprises. The debt conversion committee was set up in July 1988 to implement Nigeria's debt conversion programme. Though the appropriation of the substantial discount offered and commission paid, the nation benefited and reduced its debt stock. As a result of the strenuous effort being made by Nigeria government to formalize its economic and political relations, the prospect for an early rescheduling of Nigerian's official debts are bright especially as the international community reposes with some measures of confidence in Nigeria. In 2005/2006, Nigeria's external debt which stood at US \$32 billion was forgiven by the creditors. This has external and internal implications for the economy. On external front, Nigeria's credit worthiness increased, thereby, making the economy worthy to access short and medium term credits which enhance net capital inflows necessary for employment and growth. In the domestic economy, potential new export earnings and gains from new investment as well as the money budgeted for debt servicing are expected to be channeled into growth enhancing projects- as this result to rises in investment, employment and output. External debt service on the other hand, reduces public investment funds, employment and private income. It also reduces the country's currency and compound balance of payment problems. In view of these, several policies were introduced to reduce the magnitude of public debt, ameliorate the debt service burden in order to stimulate sustained

growth in the Nigerian economy. But, Henry observed that these policies have not been able to restrain the growth of foreign debt.

CHAPTER THREE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND MODEL SPECIFICATION, AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To fully assess the impact of external debt on economic growth, we shall receive the following models which will further throw more light on the aim of this research.

3.1.1 The theory of debt overhang

Debt overhang refers to a situation whereby an organization (A business, households or government) has existing debt so great that it cannot easily borrow more money, even when that new borrowing could be used for an investment that has a good return.

Krugman (1988) posited by defining debt overhang as a situation whereby the expected present value of the future county transfer it less than the current face value of its debt. Corden (1989)

extended the theory of debt overhang to explain a lack of motivation on the part of government to implement economic stabilization and policy reforms, in the expectation that any revenue generated by an improvement in the domestic economy will go entirely to servicing debts.

A government that has already incurred huge debt would be reluctant to borrow and invest in a project because most of the benefits will be reaped by the debt holders. In other words, any revenue generated by new investment project with a positive net present value cannot reduce the stock of debt. According to Krugman (1988, 1989) and Sachs (1989), high levels of debt imply an increase in the private sectors expected future tax burden as sovereign governments service their debt by taxing firms and households. Debt overhang characterizes a situation in which future debt burden tends to be so high that it acts as a disincentive to current investment. Lower levels of current investment will lead to lower growth and for a given tax rate, lower government revenue, lower ability to pay.

The reason adduced for most developing countries' debt is to bridge the gap between investment and savings. Unfortunately, this build-up of debts results in a debt overhang

3.1.2 Dual Gap theory

The constant need to borrow from foreign sources arises from the recognized role of capital in developmental process of any nation. Sustainable economic growth requires a given level of savings and investment and in a case where it is not sufficient, it results

in external borrowing. Herein lays the basis for the dual-gap analysis. The dual-gap theory postulates that for development to occur it requires investment and this investment is a function of savings and investment which requires domestic savings is not sufficient enough to ensure that development takes place. The dual-gap framework is coined from a national income accounting identity which states that excess investment expenditure over domestic savings is equivalent to the surplus of imports over exports. Thus at equilibrium the following identities hold;

$$I - S = m - X \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$S - M = x - m \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: I = Investment

S = Savings

M = Import

X = Export

The above equations show that the domestic resource gap (S – I) is equal to foreign exchange gap (x – m).

An excess of import over export implies an excess of resources used by an economy over resources generated by it. This further implies that the need for foreign borrowing is determined overtime by the rate of investment in relation to domestic savings.

3.1.3 Debt cum – Growth Model

In the debt cum – growth model there are two schools of thought. They are the substituting school of thought and the threshold school of thought (debt latter curve thesis). The substituting school of thought considers external debt as a substitute for savings and investment. Hence, domestic savings and investment are crowded out as a result (Krugman, 1988; Alesina and tabelline, 1990; Tomell and velusco 1992). The high marginal taxes by the creditors on the returns from investing in a country discourage domestic and foreign investments. Furthermore, the foreign savings may be used for consumption rather than investment.

On the other hand, the threshold school which emphasizes a non-linear relationship between debt and growth. According to the threshold theory, the fall in growth is due to higher distortionary tax burden on capital required to service debt. In this case debt and growth is linked

to the problem of capital flight where at high debt levels growth falls. This process leads to lower rate of return on capital, lower investment and hence lower growth.

3.1.4 The Dependency Theory

On account of the factors responsible for the position of the developing countries and their constant and continuous reliance on external borrowing for their economic growth and development, the dependency theory seeks to outline the factors that have contributed to the development of the underdeveloped countries. This theory is based on the assumption that resources flow from a “periphery” of poor and underdeveloped states to a “core” of wealthy states thereby enrich the latter at the expense of the former. The phenomenon associated with the dependency theory is that poor states are impoverished while rich ones are enriched by the way the poor states are integrated into the world system (Todaro, 2003; Amin, 1976).

Dependency theory states that the poverty of the countries in the periphery is not because they are not integrated or fully integrated into the world system as it is often argued by free market economists, but because of how they are integrated into the system. From this standpoint a common school of thought is the bourgeoisie scholars. To them the state of underdevelopment and the constant dependence of less developed countries on developed countries is as a result of their domestic mishaps. They believe this issue can be explained by their lack of close integration, diffusion of capital, low level of technology, poor institutional framework, bad

leadership, corruption, mismanagement, etc. (Momoh and Hundey, 1999). They see the under-development and dependency of the world countries as being internally inflicted rather than externally afflicted. To this school of thought, a way out of the problem is for third world countries to seek foreign assistance in terms of aid, loan, investment, etc, and allow undisrupted operations of the multinational corporations (MNCs). Due to the underdeveloped nature of the LDC's, they are dependent on the developed nations for virtually everything ranging from technology, aid, technical assistance, to culture, etc. The dependent position of most underdeveloped countries has made them vulnerable to the products of the western metropolitan countries and Breton Woods institutions (Ajayi, 2000). The dependency theory gives a detailed.

3.2 MODEL SPECIFICATION

The model is adopted from a simple open macroeconomic debt growth model employed by (Boboye and Ojo, 2012).

The model is specified of the functional form:

$$RGDP = f(EDS, DSP, EXR, INF, GCEXP, GFCF)$$

Where: RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product

EDS = External Debt Stock

DSP = External Debt Service Payments

INF = Inflation Rate

GCEXP = Government Capital Expenditure

GFCF = Gross Fixed Capital Formation

The model is specified thus:

$$RGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EDS + \beta_2 DSP + \beta_3 INF + \beta_4 GCEXP + \beta_5 GFCF + \mu \quad \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: β_0 = a constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = coefficient of the independent variables

μ = Error term

The model is specified of its log form:

$$\text{Log RGDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log EDS} + \beta_2 \text{Log DSP} + \beta_3 \text{Log INF} + \beta_4 \text{Log GCEXP} + \beta_5 \text{Log GFCF}$$

Where: Log (RGDP) = log of Real Gross Domestic Product

Log (EDS) = log of External Debt Stock

Log (DSP) = log of External Debt Service Payments

Log (INF) = log of Inflation Rate

Log (GCEXP) = log of Government Capital Expenditure

Log (GFCF) = log of Gross Fixed Capital Formation

$$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, < 0, \beta_0, \beta_4, \beta_5 > 0$$

Definition of Variables

Real Gross Domestic Product is a measure that reflects the value of goods and services produced in a given year. It is used to capture economic growth in this study because it is adjusted for inflation and as such provides a more accurate figure.

External Debt Stock is the amount at which the debt was contracted and it is used as a proxy for capturing external debt burden.

External Debt Service Payments is the amount used in repaying the external debt. It is also used as a proxy for capturing external debt burden.

Inflation is the rate at which the general price level of prices of goods and services is rising over time, resulting in a fall in the purchasing value of money

Government capital expenditure is the payments by government for the acquisition of fixed capital assets, stocks, land or intangible assets.

Gross fixed capital formation is essentially net investment. It is a component of the expenditure method of calculating GDP. In a precise form it measures the net increase in fixed capital

Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), External Debt Stock (EDS) and External Debt Service Payment (DSP) and government expenditure (GEXP) were logged due to the large nature of their values. Exchange Rate (EXR) was not logged because it is a rate.

The a priori expectation provides the expected sign and significance of the values to be estimated in the light of the economic theory and empirical evidence

Therefore;

$$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 < 0,$$

$$\beta_0, \beta_4, \beta_5 > 0$$

This means that a negative relationship exist between Real Gross Domestic Product with external debt stock and External Debt Service Payments and inflation rate. i.e. the higher the

debt service payments, external debt stock or inflation rate the lower the economic growth and vice versa. While a positive relationship between Real Gross Domestic Product and government capital expenditure and gross fixed capital formation. i.e. move in the same direction with real Gross Domestic Product.

3.3 SOURCES OF DATA

This study makes use of secondary data covering a period of 36 years i.e. 1981 – 2016 gotten from World Bank Statistical Database (WDI 2016), also annual data were used for the study and the main source of data came from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Statistical bulletin, economic and financial review and annual reports.

Data Definitions In analyzing the results obtained as regards to the validity of the variables used in terms of their statistical significance, decision making will be made based on the following criteria:

1. Signs and magnitude of the parameter: The signs (+ or -) are the economic a priori condition set by economic theory and usually refers to sign and size of parameters of economic relationships. Thus they should conform to the a priori expectations stated above.

Parameters in the model are expected to have signs and sizes that conform to economic theory, if they do they are accepted, otherwise they are rejected. Unless there is an explanation to believe that in this instance the principles of economic theory do not hold.

2. Coefficient of Determination (R^2): This shows the percentage of the total variation of the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable(s). It shows the extent to which the independent variable(s) influences the dependent variable. It is a measure of the goodness of fit of the model; the closer the R^2 is to zero the worse the fit.

3. Adjusted Coefficient of Determination (\bar{R}^2): Also the adjusted R^2 is needed because it gives a better measure of the goodness of fit having been adjusted for loss of degree of freedom as more explanatory values are added. It lies between zero and one and the closer it is to one the better the goodness of fit.

4. The t-test: It is used to determine the statistical significance of the parameters in the model. They will be tested at 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance. The rule of thumb states that $t \geq 2$ is statistically significant. Any value below this is insignificant.

5. F-statistic: It is meant to test the overall significance of the entire model as regards the dependent variable. It checks the joint variance of the explanatory variables. The level of significance to be used is 5%. Hence, if the probability is ≤ 0.05 , the explanatory variables'

parameter estimates will be jointly statistically significant. Any value greater than 5% makes them jointly statistically insignificant.

6. The Durbin-Watson statistic: The D.W. test is used to test for the presence of positive or negative autocorrelation in a model. The simple correlation matrix of the variables would be used as a guide in determining what combinations of the explanatory variables are responsible for multi-co linearity. It is a simple guide used to specify the right combination of the explanatory variables.

7. Standard Error: The standard error of estimates (SEE) will be used to measure the standard error of the stochastic term. If the standard error of the estimates is small relative to the mean value of the dependent variable, the model equation is preferred and vice versa.

3.4 TECHNIQUES OF ESTIMATION

Time series data covering a period of 36 years (i.e. 1981 – 2016), will be estimated using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) which depicts short run relationship, also Co-integration technique of analysis which is an improvement on the classical ordinary least square technique (OLS) will be used to. This technique was chosen as it depicts long-run economic growth. The following techniques of estimation are employed in carrying out the co-integration analysis:

3.4.1 Unit Root Test

This is the pre Co-integration test. It is used to determine the order of integration of a variable that is how many times it has to be differenced or not to become stationary. It is to check for the presence of a unit root in the variable i.e. whether the variable is stationary or not. The null hypothesis is that there is no unit root. This test is carried out using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) technique of estimation. The rule is that if the ADF test statistic is greater than the 5 percent critical value we accept the null hypothesis i.e. the variable is stationary but if the ADF test statistic is less than the 5 percent critical value i.e. the variable is non-stationary we reject the null hypothesis and go ahead to difference once. If the variable does not become stationary at first difference we difference twice. However it is expected that the variable becomes stationary at first difference.

3.4.2 Co-integration

The co-integration test is used to investigate if a long run relationship exists between variables in the model (Ogundipe and Alege, 2013). This test is usually carried out after the test for order of co-integration. It will be carried out using It will be carried out using Johansen co-integration technique.

3.4.3 Error Correction Model

The error correction model is appealing because of its ability to infuse flexibility by combining the short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium model in a unified system. In other words, it shows the speed of adjustment from short-run to long-run equilibrium. The apriori expectation is that the ECM coefficient must be negative and significant for errors to be corrected in the long-run. The higher the ECM, the better the variables are stationary or not and to also determine the order of integration of a variable. The order of integration of a variable implies the number of times it has to be differenced to become stationary. Its carried out using the Augmented Dicker Fuller Test (ADF).

CHAPTER FOUR

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

4.1 PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULT

This Section of the research comprises of the data presentation, estimation and results of the empirical investigation carried out. It also addresses the relationship between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria in the long run. This chapter is further divided into trend analysis which shows the trend of the time series data used from 1980-2012, descriptive analysis which contains the measures of central tendency which include mean, mode, median as well as measures of variation and other statistical characteristics of the variables and econometric analysis which included the unit root test, the Ordinary Least Square Method (this analysis did not give a desired result as it showed that the model was spurious. Hence, the need to test for cointegration using the Johansen cointegration technique which after the Error Correction Model was carried out resulting from observed conintegration of some variable in the market. This also did not yield a good result, hence the need for a higher technique, AR (1). Thereafter findings were evaluated.

4.1.1 Trend Analysis

Figure 4.1 Graphical Trend Analysis of Variables

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

Interpretation of Trend Analysis

Figure 4.2 Real gross domestic product (RGDP)

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

The trend of real gross domestic products shows that there has been an increase in real GDP between 1981 and 2016. From 1981-1990, RGDP was low and increasing at a slow rate. This could be attributed to several factors influencing the economic growth in this decade which include drastic fall in oil price, the rise in international interest on our huge external debts and domestic policy mistakes. This is the reason why this decade was referred to as the “lost decade” of development opportunities especially for Africa and Nigeria in particular (Iyoha, 1997). But

with the adoption of the Structural Adjustment Programme of 1986 which ushered in an era of laissez-faire policies and economic liberalization and other national programmes and policies however led to the continuous rise in real gross domestic product.

Figure 4.3 External debt stock (EDS)

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

It is observed to exhibit a high level of volatility in the variable. The reduction in the value is notice mainly from the period of 1986 when the Structural Adjustment Programme was adopted.

It is observed that the trend had the high level of increase during the president Olusegun Obasanjo era when Nigeria actually faced a huge debt burden.

Figure 4.4 Debt service payment (DSP)

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

From the graph above debt service payment decreasing at decreasing rate till 2000, ever since then it is observed from the graph to be increasing. Although dropped a little in 2007. This increasing rate of debt service payment is due to the weight of the country's debt burden.

Figure 4.5 Inflation (INF)

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

The trend of inflation rate shows the increase in the general price level of commodities in an economy. The trend here shows a random movement with inflation rate at its lowest in the year 1986 which was the year of the Structural Adjustment Programme at a value of 5.4%. This is because of the restriction on government expenditure and this led to a fall in aggregate demand and also a fall in the inflation rate. It was at its highest in the year 1995 at 72.8%. there is as a result in the increase in government spending and the creation of money to finance debt servicing and ever since it has been exhibiting a various movement.

Figure 4.6 Government capital expenditure (GCEXP)

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

Obviously seen from the graph government capital expenditure was very low in 1985, resulting from the fact that government expenditure during this period was invested on unproductive ventures, comprising more of consumption expenditure. From 1988 government capital expenditure started to increase, ever since it has been on the rising trend.

Figure 4.7 Gross fixed capital formations (GFCF)

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

The trend in gross fixed capital formation is observed to have decrease from the period of 1980 to 1987. This was attributed to the decrease production from the industrial sector. Hence , SAP brought an increase in the industrial sector hence, high rate of volatility.

4.1.2 Descriptive Analysis

Table 4.1 Summary Statistics

	RGDP	EDS	DSP	INF	GCEXP	GFCF
Mean	31757148	1125073.	256245.9	20.20135	368149.5	4629057.
Median	22391139	593184.5	74810.66	12.91927	255670.0	2804752.
Maximum	69023930	4890269.	1584109.	76.75887	1152796.	10570467
Minimum	13779255	2331.200	1007.078	0.223606	4100.100	1798576.
Std. Dev.	18151714	1393396.	362499.7	18.71449	372331.4	2993598.
Skewness	0.874864	1.403746	1.967699	1.571310	0.654022	0.867355
Kurtosis	2.318378	3.716818	6.724516	4.457559	2.058879	2.129455
Jarque-Bera	5.289229	12.59376	44.03907	18.00082	3.895033	5.650597
Probability	0.071033	0.001842	0.000000	0.000123	0.142628	0.059291
Sum	1.14E+09	40502643	9224852.	727.2487	13253384	1.67E+08
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.15E+16	6.80E+13	4.60E+12	12258.12	4.85E+12	3.14E+14
Observations	36	36	36	36	36	36

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

Mean is the average value of the series which is gotten by dividing the total value of the series by the number of observations. From the above table we see that the mean for LOGRGDP (Real Gross Domestic Product), LOGEDS (External Debt Stock), LOGDSP (Debt Service Payments) LOGINF (Inflation) LOGGCEXP (Government Capital Expenditure) and LOGGFCF (Gross Fixed Capital Formation) are 31757148, 1125073, 256245.9, 20.20135, 368149.5 and 4629057 respectively.

Median is the middle value of the series when the values are arranged in an ascending order. From the table the median for LOGRGDP, LOGEDS, LOGDSP LOGINF, LOGGCEXP and LOGFCF are 22391139, 593184.5, 74810.66, 12.91927, 255670.0, and 2804752 respectively.

Maximum and minimum are the maximum and minimum values of the series the series in the current sample. The maximum and minimum values for LOGRGDP, LOGEDS, LOGDSP LOGINF, LOGGCEXP and LOGFCF are 69023930 & 13779255, 4890269 & 2331.200, 1584109 & 1007.078, 76.75887 & 0.223606, 1152796 & 4100.100, and 10570467 & 1798576 respectively..

Standard Deviation is a measure of spread or dispersion in the series. From table above the standard deviation for LOGRGDP, LOGEDS, LOGDSP LOGINF, LOGGCEXP and LOGFCF is 18151714, 1393396, 362499.7, 18.71449, 372331.4 and 2993598.respectively.

Skewness is a measure of assymetry of the distribution of the series around its mean. The skewness of a normal distribution is zero. Positive skewness implies that the distribution has a long right tail and negative skewness implies that the distribution has a long left tail. From the above table we observe that LOGRGDP LOGEDS, LOGDSP LOGINF, LOGGCEXP and LOGFCF all have positive skewness and as such they have long right tails.

Kurtosis measures the peakedness or flatness of the distribution of the series. If the kurtosis is above three, the distribution is peaked or leptokurtic relative to the normal and if the kurtosis is less than three, the distribution is flat or platykurtic relative to normal. From table 4.1 above only

LOGEDS, LOGDSP, and LOGINF exceeds three therefore they are peaked or leptokurtic while LOGRGDP, LOGGCEXP, and LOGGFCF are below three therefore they are flat or platykurtic. Jarque-bera is a test statistic to test for normal distribution of the series. It measures the difference of the skewness and kurtosis of the series with those with normal distribution. From the table above the Jarque-bera for LOGRGDP LOGEDS, LOGDSP LOGINF, LOGGCEXP and LOGFCF are 5.289229, 12.59376, 44.03907, 18.00082, 3.895033, and 5.650597. The Jarque-bera statistic LOGEDS, LOGDSP, AND LOGINF is seen from the table to be statistically significant at 5% level of significance, while that of LOGRGDP, LOGGCEXP, and LOGGFCF are not statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

4.2 ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS

This section presents the regression results, as well as their interpretation. The study has attempted to empirically determine the impact of government education expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria.

One of the problems with some empirical investigations is that the data used in estimation is not appropriately tested. When dealing with time series data, it is important to estimate whether the series of data are stationary or not because the regression of non-stationary series may yield spurious results which may pose some dangerous policy implications.

The standard method is used in identifying stationary time series is Unit Root test. The most commonly used Unit Root test is the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test which was used in this study.

4.2.1 Unit Root Test

This test tries to examine the property of the variables. It is used to check for the presence of a unit root i.e. no stationarity of the variables. This test is carried out using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test. This is the first test carried out in the Co-integration analysis and is known as the pre Co-integration test. First, we test all variables for stationarity at log levels.

The ADF is carried out using Eviews software package and the results from the test are tabulated below:

Table 4.2 Augmented Dickey Fuller Test Results at Levels

VARIABLES	ADF STATISTICS	5% LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE FOR ADF STATISTICS	PROB*	LAG	REMARKS
LNRGDP	0.097327	-2.951125	0.9609	2	Non-stationary
LNEDS	-3.210580	-2.948404	0.0278	2	Stationary

LN DSP	-1.105796	-2.948404	0.7025	2	Non-stationary
LN INF	-4.986379	-2.948404	0.0003	2	Stationary
LN GCEXP	-1.274337	-2.948404	0.6304	2	Non-stationary
LN GFCF	-0.904965	-2.948404	0.7748	2	Non-stationary

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

Based on the ADF statistics to check for unit roots in the time series variable, it is shown that the log value of RGDP, DSP, GCEXP and GFCF was non-stationary at all levels as the ADF statistics were less than the critical values and each probability values greater than 0.05. This provides the justification for differencing the variables.

Taking the first difference of each of the variables, the Augmented Dickey Fuller Test results at first difference is shown in the table below

VARIABLES	ADF STATISTICS	5% LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE FOR ADF STATISTICS	PROB*	LAG	REMARKS
RGDP	-3.229356	-3.639407	0.0268	2	Stationary

Table 4.3 Augmented Dickey Fuller Test Results at First Difference source:

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

Based on the ADF statistics, it is shown that all the variables (RGDP, EDS, DSP, INF, GCEXP and GFCF) are stationary at first difference as their respective ADF statistic were greater than the critical value at 5% level of significance and also, their respective probabilities were less than 0.05. Since stationary was found in at least two variables of order 1 (0); and order 1 (1) for all the variables, we are justified to conduct co-integration and Error Correction Model among the variables.

4.2.2 Test of Cointegration

The co-integration test is used to check for long run relationship between the dependent and independent variables (Ogundipe and Amaghionyeodiwe, 2013). The co-integration test was carried out using the Johansen technique also using Eviews software package and it produced the following results:

Table 4.4 (a)for Johansen Co-integration Using Trace Statistic

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.805039	127.5600	95.75366	0.0001
At most 1 *	0.689219	71.97149	69.81889	0.0333
At most 2	0.314543	32.23686	47.85613	0.5991

At most 3	0.270904	19.39607	29.79707	0.4647
At most 4	0.149192	8.653764	15.49471	0.3984
At most 5	0.088764	3.160422	3.841466	0.0754
Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Author's computation using E-views 7.0

The result of the cointegration test shows that both the trace statistics confirm that there exist 2 cointegration equations among the variables of interest.

Table 4.4 (b) Test for Johansen Co-integration Using Max-Eigen Value

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.805039	55.58852	40.07757	0.0004
At most 1 *	0.689219	39.73463	33.87687	0.0089

At most 2	0.314543	12.84078	27.58434	0.8935
At most 3	0.270904	10.74231	21.13162	0.6730
At most 4	0.149192	5.493342	14.26460	0.6787
At most 5	0.088764	3.160422	3.841466	0.0754
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

From the above 2 tables in summary the trace indicates two co-integrating equation at 5 percent level, while the Max-Eigen value indicates one co-integrating equation at 5 percent level. Based on the above tables we reject the null hypothesis of no co-integrating equations. This is because both the trace and the maximum Eigen value tests indicate the presence of 3 co-integration equations among the variables for long run convergence at 5% level.

4.2.3 Error Correction Model

Presentation and Interpretation of ECM Result

Table 4.5 (a): Table Showing Error Correction Estimates

Dependent Variable: D(LNRGDP)		
Method: Least Squares		

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.035277	0.007386	4.776179	0.0001
D(LNEDS)	0.006695	0.005523	1.212309	0.2355
D(LNDSP)	0.009617	0.016759	0.573813	0.5707
D(LNINF)	-0.008562	0.005478	-1.562967	0.1293
D(LNGCEXP)	0.030147	0.022679	1.329291	0.1945
D(LNGFCF)	0.118709	0.027419	4.329468	0.0002
ECM(-1)	-2.58E-09	2.55E-09	-1.011619	0.3204
R-squared	0.476677	Mean dependent var		0.042668
Adjusted R-squared	0.364536	Durbin-Watson stat		0.996297
F-statistic Prob(F-statistic)	4.250699 0.003644	Akaike info criterion		-3.730951
Schwarz criterion	3.419881	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.623570

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

From the ECM result above, it can be seen that the ECM's Coefficient is negative and t-statistics is not significant. Also, the D-W of 0.996297 shows the presence of autocorrelation. this technique also did not give us a desirable result as R-Square is 0.476677 and R –Squared adjusted of 0.364536 showing that very low percentage of the dependent variable was explained by the independent variables making thus the need for a higher technique.

Presentation and Interpretation of AR Result

Table 4.6: Table Showing AR Result

Dependent Variable: D(LNRGDP)				
Method: Least Squares				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.040412	0.013539	2.984966	0.0061

D(LNEDS)	0.008998	0.003131	2.873407	0.0080
D(LNDSP)	0.005100	0.010333	0.493533	0.6258
D(LNINF)	-0.009905	0.003065	-3.231610	0.0033
D(LNGCEXP)	0.038667	0.016719	2.312728	0.0289
D(LNGFCF)	0.063056	0.021376	2.949848	0.0066
ECM(-1)	-4.93E-09	2.11E-09	-2.335723	0.0275
AR(1)	0.657835	0.136878	4.806008	0.0001
R-squared	0.702558	Mean dependent var		0.044454
Adjusted R-squared	0.622477	Durbin-Watson stat		2.176215
F-statistic	8.773135	Akaike info criterion		-4.258569
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000016	Hannan-Quinn criterion		-4.136090
Schwarz criterion	-3.899425			

Source: Author's Compilation Using Eviews 7

4.3 ANALYSIS OF RESULT

The error correction model is an extension and generalization of the traditional approach to modeling short run dynamics and long run disequilibrium. After using our adjustment techniques i.e. the AR maximum likelihood, it can be seen from our result that some of our variables did not conform to a-prior expectation i.e economic/theoretical expectation except INF, GCEXP, and GFCF.

Coefficient of determination R^2 and its adjusted counterpart R^2

The coefficient of determination in table 4.3 is 0.70. The adjusted R-squared is 0.62. This means that 70 percent of the variations in RGDP can be explained by all the explanatory variables; RGDP, EDS, DSP, INF, GCEXP, and GFCF. This is a good fit as only about 30 percent of the systematic variation was left unexplained systematic variation is left unexplained. We attribute this unexplained variation to variables not explicitly included in the model and measurement errors both of which effects are captured by the random error term.

T- Statistics

The statistics test of the significance of each variable in the model. From the result, all the variable in the model are individually significance since the probability value is less than 0.05, i.e. at 5% .significance level. Except for debt service payment (DSP) variable.

The F-statistics

The F-test is a test of the overall significance of the model. It tests the hypothesis that all the variables taken together are not significantly different from zero; i.e

$$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = 0$$

The value of the F-statistic is 8.77. The probability value of the F-statistic is 0.00. This is less than 0.05. Thus, the F-statistic shows that the model is statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected and the hypothesis that the slope coefficients are simultaneously and significantly different from zero is accepted. This implies that the overall model is significant in explaining the variations in RGDP.

DW Statistics

The Durbin- Watson Statistic of 2.17621 reveals the absence of autocorrelation in the model using the rule of thumb which states that when the DW value is close to 2, there is absence of autocorrelation in the model.

Given the soundness of goodness of fit as analyzed above, we can therefore rely on the estimated parameters of the variables. The $D(LNRGDP)$, $D(LNEDS)$, $D(LNINF)$, $D(LNGCEXP)$, $D(LNGFCF)$ and the intercept is statistically significant as their p-values are 0.0061, 0.0080, 0.0033, 0.0289 and 0.0066 respectively, at 5% level of significance since their p-values fall below 0.05. Thus, we conclude that all of our exogenous variables are statistically significant at first differencing. Except for $D(LNDSP)$.

The coefficient of the error correction term ECM is $-4.93E-09$. This is negative, as expected and it is statistically significant at 5% levels of significance as the t value is on the grey region of indecision. Thus, we can conclude that it can successfully perform the function of correcting the short run dynamics and the long run equilibrium.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the result obtained, the variables INF, GCEXP, GFCF are as priori stated, as there was negative, positive and positive relationship respectively between these variables and the RGDP. This implies that gross fixed capital formation and government capital expenditure will positively increase the growth of the Nigerian economy by a greater percentage. This result signifies that these variables are agents of growth in the Nigerian economy as observed by the result and these variables are statistically significant. Also inflation rate affects economic growth negatively, and it is statistically significant too. EDS, and DSP did not meet a priori expectation as they were observed to be moving in the same direction with RGDP. This means that in the short run, as debt increases, this can be due to the fact that the more debt accumulated, the more the money in the country, thus an increase in GDP will tend to occur, though depicting growth in the short run, it may have an adverse effect in the long run if not adequately managed. This is in line with the postulate of Keynesian theory that debt would enhance economic growth. In the same vein, Suliman et al (2012) carried out a study on the effect of external debt on the economic growth of Nigeria. Annual time series data covering the period from 1970-2010 was used. The empirical

analysis was carried out using econometric techniques of Ordinary least squares (OLS), Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test, Johansen Co-integration test and error correction method. The co-integration test shows long-run relationship amongst the variables and findings from the error correction model revealed that external debt has contribute positively to the growth of the Nigerian economy. Also DSP is observed to negate apriori expectation, but this variable is not statistically significant at 1% and 5% level of significance. But the EDS variable is statistically significant having its p-vlue as 0.0061.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

In this study, an attempt has been made empirically to establish the impact of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria. To empirically show this relationship for the period 1981-2016, an econometric model was constructed using real gross domestic product (RGDP) as the dependent variable, while External debt stock (EDS), Debt service payment (DSP), Inflation rate (INF), Government capital expenditure (GCEXP) and Gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) were used as the independent variables.

In the study, the time series data were tested for stationarity using Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test. Finally, the error correction model (ECM) was employed, also AR (1). The ECM coefficient was negative and significant showing that it can successfully perform the function of correcting the short run dynamics. The Error Correction result from the multiple regression performed on the model revealed that all the variables accounted for approximately 70% variations in the real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. Thus, the series of test conducted produced good results for policy simulation.

Summarily therefore, some of the findings obtained from the study are;

1. External debt stock is positively related to economic growth in Nigeria. This relationship was found to be significant.
2. Debt service payment was also found to positively and insignificantly related to economic growth.
3. Inflation rate is also observed to be negatively and statistically significantly related to economic growth.
4. Also observed from the result Government capital expenditure is positively related to economic growth in Nigeria. Also this relationship is seen to be statistically significant.
5. Furthermore, gross fixed capital formation was seen to be negatively related to economic growth in Nigeria.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

From the results obtained from the study, the following recommendations are suggested.

1. Loans contracted should be invested in profitable ventures, which will generate a reasonable amount of money for debt repayment. External debt finance should be used only for projects of highest priority such as mineral resources, education and agricultural projects
2. the Nigerian government should promote exportation of domestic products as a high exchange rate will make our goods more attractive in the foreign market and will increase foreign exchange earnings.

3. Anticorruption agencies like Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Independent Corrupt Practices and other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) and Code of Conduct Bureau should be made independent and the laws establishing them reviewed by government to make them more functional and efficient. This will reduce the incidences of misappropriation and embezzlement of funds from external debt.
4. The authorities responsible for managing Nigeria's external debt should adequately keep track of the debt payment obligations and the debt should not be allowed to pass a maximum limit so as to avoid debt overhang..
5. Lastly foreign borrowing by private and public organizations should be adequately monitored by the government debt agency – Debt Management Office (DMO) and all the external loans contracted should be reported to the agency so that an up to date record of the volume of debt can be kept. Transparency and accountability are high on the agenda of modern debt management practices.

5.3 CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria. External debts are necessary to meet shortfall internal resources, and stimulate the economy. However, it must be properly utilized to avoid serious consequences. Borrowing is not the most important issue but the use to which the fund is deployed. This should be the most important thing agitating the mind of any good accountant and

Economist whenever external debt is contemplated. It should be approached with caution, ensuring optimal utilization and higher return than the interest (cost of fund).

In this study Real gross domestic product was used as a proxy for economic growth which is the dependent variable while external debt stock, external debt service payments and exchange rate were the independent variables. External debt stock and external debt service payments were used to capture the external debt burden in Nigeria. Also Inflation rate, government capital expenditure and gross fixed capital formation.

The Johansen co-integration test was used to test the first hypothesis of no long run relationship between external debt and economic growth. The null hypothesis was accepted as the results showed no long run relationship between external debt and economic growth. In the Error correction model, all the exogenous variable was statistically significant, except Debt service payment.

Based on these findings recommendations were given.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Table of Data

year	RGDP	EDS	INF	GCEXP	GFCF
1981	16.54061	7.754138	2.785628	8.789812	15.99277
1982	16.52257	9.084709	1.937302	8.766737	15.73855
1983	16.44378	9.266503	3.657647	8.494068	15.31663
1984	16.43867	9.60297	3.119276	8.318767	14.8704
1985	16.52048	9.758496	0.029559	8.606065	14.81276
1986	16.5393	10.6323	2.615204	9.050969	14.67134
1987	16.541	11.52079	2.271589	8.759747	14.40251
1988	16.60147	11.80527	4.114329	9.02883	14.44612
1989	16.66591	12.39003	3.799303	9.618076	14.46592
1990	16.77591	12.60691	1.284825	10.08783	14.7927
1991	16.77037	12.70215	3.133741	10.25206	14.78888
1992	16.79207	13.20719	3.88773	10.5907	14.75848
1993	16.80764	13.35845	4.115164	10.90599	14.90685
1994	16.8102	11.08031	4.340669	11.16928	14.79973
1995	16.82875	13.48264	3.943353	11.70469	14.49598
1996	16.86847	13.33314	2.661258	12.2687	14.6623
1997	16.89692	13.29788	2.323694	12.50489	14.747
1998	16.92157	13.35825	2.477624	12.64115	14.6951
1999	16.92677	7.854526	-1.49787	13.11841	14.66541
2000	16.98049	14.94607	2.676007	12.3861	14.82268
2001	17.04503	14.97122	2.803048	12.99156	14.57797
2002	17.18135	15.18488	2.498854	12.68037	14.76312

2003	17.27213	15.31476	3.170163	12.3954	15.16951
2004	17.37145	15.40276	2.303433	12.7694	14.89501
2005	17.43918	14.80694	2.447996	13.16062	14.78454
2006	17.50428	13.02025	2.145782	13.222	15.25071
2007	17.5749	12.99201	1.881593	13.54018	15.59945
2008	17.64442	13.16782	2.711748	13.77562	15.59217
2009	17.72465	13.28862	2.634013	13.9577	15.89056
2010	17.81577	13.44421	2.4681	13.69207	16.03287
2011	17.86749	13.70662	2.330495	13.73055	15.9468
2012	17.90869	13.84206	2.483329	13.68179	15.972
2013	17.96211	14.14289	2.074037	13.91842	16.04771
2014	18.02248	14.30502	2.076725	13.57104	16.17357
2015	18.04996	14.56292	2.256541	13.61506	16.16041
2016	18.03401	15.06223	2.92047	13.36107	16.15078

Appendix 2: Table of Logged Data

year	RGDP	EDS	DSP	INF	GCEXP	GFCF
1981	16.54061	7.754138	6.934794	2.785628	8.789812	15.99277
1982	16.52257	9.084709	7.062334	1.937302	8.766737	15.73855
1983	16.44378	9.266503	6.914809	3.657647	8.494068	15.31663
1984	16.43867	9.60297	7.119084	3.119276	8.318767	14.8704
1985	16.52048	9.758496	7.381534	0.029559	8.606065	14.81276
1986	16.5393	10.6323	7.397313	2.615204	9.050969	14.67134
1987	16.541	11.52079	8.276127	2.271589	8.759747	14.40251
1988	16.60147	11.80527	9.131156	4.114329	9.02883	14.44612
1989	16.66591	12.39003	9.49354	3.799303	9.618076	14.46592
1990	16.77591	12.60691	10.07838	1.284825	10.08783	14.7927
1991	16.77037	12.70215	10.18166	3.133741	10.25206	14.78888
1992	16.79207	13.20719	9.873042	3.88773	10.5907	14.75848
1993	16.80764	13.35845	11.30321	4.115164	10.90599	14.90685
1994	16.8102	11.08031	10.80771	4.340669	11.16928	14.79973
1995	16.82875	13.48264	10.84073	3.943353	11.70469	14.49598

1996	16.86847	13.33314	10.87894	2.661258	12.2687	14.6623
1997	16.89692	13.29788	11.13517	2.323694	12.50489	14.747
1998	16.92157	13.35825	11.07278	2.477624	12.64115	14.6951
1999	16.92677	7.854526	10.33668	-1.49787	13.11841	14.66541
2000	16.98049	14.94607	11.78332	2.676007	12.3861	14.82268
2001	17.04503	14.97122	11.95386	2.803048	12.99156	14.57797
2002	17.18135	15.18488	12.00647	2.498854	12.68037	14.76312
2003	17.27213	15.31476	12.80356	3.170163	12.3954	15.16951
2004	17.37145	15.40276	12.85449	2.303433	12.7694	14.89501
2005	17.43918	14.80694	12.88401	2.447996	13.16062	14.78454
2006	17.50428	13.02025	12.42652	2.145782	13.222	15.25071
2007	17.5749	12.99201	12.27246	1.881593	13.54018	15.59945
2008	17.64442	13.16782	12.85108	2.711748	13.77562	15.59217
2009	17.72465	13.28862	12.43635	2.634013	13.9577	15.89056
2010	17.81577	13.44421	12.93762	2.4681	13.69207	16.03287
2011	17.86749	13.70662	13.1753	2.330495	13.73055	15.9468
2012	17.90869	13.84206	13.42882	2.483329	13.68179	15.972
2013	17.96211	14.14289	13.62689	2.074037	13.91842	16.04771
2014	18.02248	14.30502	13.75544	2.076725	13.57104	16.17357
2015	18.04996	14.56292	13.87414	2.256541	13.61506	16.16041
2016	18.03401	15.06223	14.27553	2.92047	13.36107	16.15078

Logged result

Dependent Variable: LNRGDP

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/10/18 Time: 02:26

Sample: 1981 2016

Included observations: 36

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	9.753252	0.633725	15.39036	0.0000
LNEDS	0.008639	0.022139	0.390221	0.6991
LNDSF	0.164529	0.039319	4.184481	0.0002
LNINF	-0.041574	0.020575	-2.020665	0.0523
LNGCEXP	0.002743	0.033032	0.083035	0.9344
LNGFCF	0.364855	0.040076	9.104018	0.0000

R-squared	0.965096	Mean dependent var	17.12808
Adjusted R-squared	0.959279	S.D. dependent var	0.535484
			-1.46129
S.E. of regression	0.108058	Akaike info criterion	4
			-1.19737
Sum squared resid	0.350293	Schwarz criterion	5
			-1.36917
Log likelihood	32.30330	Hannan-Quinn criter.	9
F-statistic	165.9024	Durbin-Watson stat	1.032599
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Unit root test for lnrgdp at first difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LNRGDP) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=2)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.229356	0.0268
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: D(LNRGDP,2)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/10/18 Time: 02:21

Sample (adjusted): 1983 2016

Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
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D(LNRGDP(-1))	-0.489415	0.151552	-3.229356	0.0029
C	0.021788	0.009240	2.358026	0.0246

R-squared	0.245794	Mean dependent var	6.15E-05
Adjusted R-squared	0.222225	S.D. dependent var	0.041875
			-3.70255
S.E. of regression	0.036930	Akaike info criterion	6
			-3.61277
Sum squared resid	0.043643	Schwarz criterion	0
			-3.67193
Log likelihood	64.94346	Hannan-Quinn criter.	7
F-statistic	10.42874	Durbin-Watson stat	1.898816
Prob(F-statistic)	0.002867		

Unit root test for lneds at first difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LNEDS) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=2)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-9.119486	0.0000

Test critical values:	1% level	-3.639407
	5% level	-2.951125
	10% level	-2.614300

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: D(LNEDS,2)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/10/18 Time: 16:33

Sample (adjusted): 1983 2016

Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNEDS(-1))	-1.438110	0.157696	-9.119486	0.0000
C	0.263545	0.270148	0.975555	0.3366

				-0.02444
R-squared	0.722138	Mean dependent var		9
Adjusted R-squared	0.713455	S.D. dependent var		2.922518
S.E. of regression	1.564422	Akaike info criterion		3.789932
Sum squared resid	78.31729	Schwarz criterion		3.879718
Log likelihood	-62.42884	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.820552
F-statistic	83.16502	Durbin-Watson stat		2.198487
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Unit root test for Indsp at first difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LNDSP) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=2)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-7.541129	0.0000
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: D(LNDSP,2)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/10/18 Time: 16:34

Sample (adjusted): 1983 2016

Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNDSP(-1))	-1.281846	0.169981	-7.541129	0.0000
C	0.269677	0.087850	3.069757	0.0043

R-squared	0.639918	Mean dependent var	0.008054
Adjusted R-squared	0.628665	S.D. dependent var	0.772289
S.E. of regression	0.470612	Akaike info criterion	1.387455
Sum squared resid	7.087206	Schwarz criterion	1.477241
Log likelihood	-21.58673	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.418074
F-statistic	56.86863	Durbin-Watson stat	2.048447
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Unit root test for lninf at first difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LNINF) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=2)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-6.477353	0.0000
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.646342	
5% level	-2.954021	
10% level	-2.615817	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LNINF,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 07/10/18 Time: 16:36
 Sample (adjusted): 1984 2016
 Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNINF(-1))	-1.859042	0.287006	-6.477353	0.0000
D(LNINF(-1),2)	0.320973	0.169777	1.890560	0.0684
C	-0.024029	0.227048	-0.105831	0.9164

				-0.03201
R-squared	0.740856	Mean dependent var		3
Adjusted R-squared	0.723580	S.D. dependent var		2.480521
S.E. of regression	1.304151	Akaike info criterion		3.455489
Sum squared resid	51.02429	Schwarz criterion		3.591536
Log likelihood	-54.01558	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.501265
F-statistic	42.88285	Durbin-Watson stat		2.019576
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Unit root test for lngcexp at first difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LNGCEXP) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=2)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.833510	0.0000
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.639407	
5% level	-2.951125	
10% level	-2.614300	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LNGCEXP,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 07/10/18 Time: 16:37
 Sample (adjusted): 1983 2016
 Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNGCEXP(-1))	-1.048890	0.179804	-5.833510	0.0000
C	0.142066	0.062810	2.261845	0.0306

			-0.00679
R-squared	0.515371	Mean dependent var	2
Adjusted R-squared	0.500226	S.D. dependent var	0.473379
S.E. of regression	0.334654	Akaike info criterion	0.705582
Sum squared resid	3.583780	Schwarz criterion	0.795368
Log likelihood	-9.994890	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.736201
F-statistic	34.02984	Durbin-Watson stat	1.932253
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002		

Unit root test for lngfcf at first difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LNGFCF) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 2 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=2)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.258385	0.0256
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.653730	
5% level	-2.957110	
10% level	-2.617434	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LNGFCF,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 07/10/18 Time: 16:38
 Sample (adjusted): 1985 2016
 Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNGFCF(-1))	-0.709928	0.217877	-3.258385	0.0029
D(LNGFCF(-1),2)	-0.142730	0.169082	-0.844147	0.4057
D(LNGFCF(-2),2)	-0.453427	0.137127	-3.306624	0.0026
C	0.039572	0.030126	1.313547	0.1997

R-squared	0.674350	Mean dependent var	0.013644
Adjusted R-squared	0.639459	S.D. dependent var	0.281358
			-0.60205
S.E. of regression	0.168942	Akaike info criterion	7
			-0.41884
Sum squared resid	0.799157	Schwarz criterion	0
			-0.54132
Log likelihood	13.63291	Hannan-Quinn criter.	6
F-statistic	19.32727	Durbin-Watson stat	2.066370
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001		

Johnhasen conintegration test

Date: 07/10/18 Time: 01:49

Sample (adjusted): 1983 2016

Included observations: 34 after adjustments

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: LNRGDP LNEDES LNDSP LNINF LNGCEXP

LNGFCF

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized	Trace	0.05		
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.805039	127.5600	95.75366	0.0001
At most 1 *	0.689219	71.97149	69.81889	0.0333
At most 2	0.314543	32.23686	47.85613	0.5991
At most 3	0.270904	19.39607	29.79707	0.4647
At most 4	0.149192	8.653764	15.49471	0.3984
At most 5	0.088764	3.160422	3.841466	0.0754

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized	Max-Eigen	0.05		
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**

None *	0.805039	55.58852	40.07757	0.0004
At most 1 *	0.689219	39.73463	33.87687	0.0089
At most 2	0.314543	12.84078	27.58434	0.8935
At most 3	0.270904	10.74231	21.13162	0.6730
At most 4	0.149192	5.493342	14.26460	0.6787
At most 5	0.088764	3.160422	3.841466	0.0754

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level